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Incorporating Failure Criteria into the Collagen Recruitment Model of Tendon Viscoelasticity

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Abstract

Predicting the circumstances under which tendon failure may occur is vital in the prevention of tendon injury. This project aims to derive a mathematical model which displays the mechanical response and material properties of a tendon under an imposed strain, incorporating viscoelasticity to account for the time-dependence of the mechanical response and strain and stress-based failure criteria. More specifically, we investigate the outcome of assuming viscoelasticity by incorporating a relaxation function. Our model is based on the collagen recruitment model first developed by Lanir [[Lanir, 1983](#)], which considers the effects of microscopic tendon mechanics; therefore it is vital to first investigate the tendon structure at a microscopic level. To my knowledge, this is the first time that both viscoelasticity and failure have been incorporated into a collagen recruitment model. We discover that imposing failure criteria on a microscopic level can explain tendon behaviour on the macroscopic level when investigating the circumstances under which a tendon may fail.

Introduction

Tendon mechanics is a widely researched area with many practical advantages of study in physiology and medicine, therefore this topic should be of interest to any professionals who work in these fields. This paper suggests that knowledge of the micro-structural components of the tendon leads to an increased understanding of macro-structural mechanical behaviour. This is useful as a comprehensive understanding of the material behaviour of a tendon can help medical professionals to make judgements about the circumstances under which a tendon may fail. This can help explain the causes of injury.

In this dissertation, we develop a model which is derived from the micro-structural components of the tendon which successfully demonstrates the macroscopic viscoelastic behaviour which tendons display. We then add in failure criteria which will lead to a model that can produce a graph which is a good qualitative fit to experimental data. To understand this model, it is vital to first lay out the biological components which make up the microscopic structural elements in the tendon. A tendon is a fibrous soft tissue with a hierarchical structure, microscopic investigation of the structure throughout the hierarchy leads to an explanation of the macroscopic material behaviour of an entire tendon. It is necessary to provide structural detail on the arrangement of the collagen molecules which make up a large proportion of the mass of the fibrils, to fully explain tendon behaviour. In chapter one, the biological background of the tendon is laid out and an overview of the typical material behaviour we expect a tendon to exhibit is given. The background of the collagen recruitment model and its assumptions are then introduced. The collagen recruitment model is a model where fibrils only contribute to stiffness when taut and can demonstrate the viscoelasticity of a tendon.

To add viscoelasticity to the collagen recruitment model, we must first lay out linear viscoelastic constitutive models. In chapter two, three rheological models are introduced namely, the Maxwell model, the Kelvin-Voigt model and the Standard linear solid model. The creep-recovery and stress-relaxation responses of these models are then explored and compared with the known tendon responses to these tests. This allows us to then choose a constitutive equation derived from a rheological model which successfully captures the viscoelastic behaviour of a tendon to incorporate into our model. Once we have a constitutive equation, the mathematics of the collagen recruitment model is explained in detail in chapter three and the constitutive equation which models viscoelasticity can be incorporated.

In chapter four the graphical results produced by our model are investigated under various loading conditions. Evaluation of these graphs allows us to conclude whether the developed model is successful in demonstrating tendon material properties. Once the adequacy of the model's ability to predict tendon mechanical behaviour has been decided, we can introduce failure criteria into the model. The likely conditions under which tendons fail are discussed in chapter five before various failure criteria based on either strain or stress are introduced. We investigate the effects of imposing failure criteria on both the microscopic and macroscopic levels by comparing them with the behaviour of a real-life tendon failing. This leads us to make conclusions about which failure criteria produce results which best fit real-life data collected in experiments investigating tendon failure.

Contents

1	Biological Background and Material Behaviour	5
1.1	Collagen Molecules	5
1.1.1	Formation of Fibrils	6
1.1.2	Fibril Crimping	6
1.2	Tendon Structure	7
1.2.1	Additional Components of the Tendon	8
1.3	Material Behaviour	8
1.3.1	Stress	9
1.3.2	Strain	9
1.3.3	Stiffness, Strength and Toughness	9
1.3.4	A Typical Tendon Stress-Strain Curve	9
1.3.5	Elasticity, Plasticity and Viscoelasticity	10
1.4	Introducing the Collagen Recruitment Model	12
1.4.1	Sequential Straightening and Loading	12
1.4.2	The Collagen Recruitment Model	12
2	Linear Viscoelastic Constitutive Models	14
2.1	Introduction to Rheological Models	14
2.1.1	The Spring	14
2.1.2	The Dash-Pot	15
2.2	The Maxwell Model	16
2.2.1	Creep-Recovery Response	17
2.2.2	Stress-Relaxation Response	18
2.3	The Kelvin-Voigt Model	19
2.3.1	Creep-Recovery Response	20
2.3.2	Stress-Relaxation Response	21
2.4	The Standard Linear Solid Model	22
2.4.1	Creep-Recovery Response	23
2.4.2	Stress-Relaxation Response	24
2.4.3	Generalized Models	26
3	Mathematical Background for The Collagen Recruitment Model	28
3.1	Matrix Response	28
3.2	Single Fibril Response	29
3.3	Fibre Response	31
3.4	Tendon Response	31

3.5	Incorporating Viscoelasticity into the Collagen Recruitment Model	32
3.6	Viscoelastic Tendon Response	33
4	Graphical Results for the Viscoelastic Collagen Recruitment Model	35
4.1	Investigating the Effects of the Fibril Volume Fraction	35
4.2	Loading at Maximum Strain	37
4.2.1	Single Fibril Response	37
4.2.2	Total Fibre Response	37
4.2.3	Tendon Response	38
4.3	Loading at a Linearly Increasing Strain	39
4.3.1	Single Fibril Response	40
4.3.2	Total Fibre Response	41
4.3.3	Tendon Response	42
4.4	Cyclic Loading	43
5	Introducing Failure into the Viscoelastic Collagen Recruitment Model	46
5.1	Failure Criteria	46
5.2	Incorporating Failure into the Mathematical Model	49
5.2.1	Strain-Based Failure	49
5.2.2	Stress-Based Failure	50
5.3	Graphical Results	51
5.3.1	Microscopic Level	51
5.3.2	Macroscopic Level	51
5.4	Discussion	52
6	Conclusion	55
6.1	Summary of Key Findings	55
6.2	Further Work	55
	Appendices	56
A	Step Functions	57
A.1	Heaviside Function	57
A.2	Dirac Function	57
B	Laplace Transforms	58
B.1	58
B.2	58
B.3	58
B.4	58
B.5	59
B.6	59
B.7	59
B.8	59
C	The Convolution Theorem	60

D Mathematica Code for The Collagen Recruitment Model	61
D.1 Linearly Increasing Strain	61
D.2 Loaded to Max Strain	62
D.3 Cyclic Loading	63
D.4 Strain-Based Failure	64
D.4.1 Micro-Scale	64
D.4.2 Macro-Scale	64
D.5 Stress-Based Failure	64
D.5.1 Micro-Scale	64
D.5.2 Macro-Scale	65
Bibliography	66

Chapter 1

Biological Background and Material Behaviour

1.1 Collagen Molecules

Collagen molecules are amongst the most abundant and varied structured fibrous proteins, present in both hard and soft tissue with complex hierarchical structures [Fratzl, 2008]. Whilst there are many forms of collagen types, I shall focus on type I as this is the type that mostly forms the fibrils which make up the tissue in tendons. In general, collagen is a molecule composed of three polypeptide chains, known as alpha chains [Hulmes, 2008], with each alpha chain containing at least one region characterized by a repeating amino acid motif. Amino acids are organic compounds that mainly consist of nitrogen, carbon, hydrogen and oxygen, these molecules combine to form proteins. The regular arrangement of amino acids in these chains is a distinguishing feature of collagen with the sequence following either a Gly-Pro-X or Gly-X-Hyp motif where X may be any of the three amino acid residues [Szpak, 2011]. Gly signifies glycine, whilst Pro and Hyp signify proline and hydroxyproline respectively. Amino acids are organic molecules made up of a basic amino group, an acidic carboxyl group and an organic R group which is a unique side chain that makes up the rest of the amino acid. Amino acids are the building blocks of proteins such as collagen. The size of an alpha chain is typically 337 to 343 repeating motifs forming either a homotrimeric molecule, defined to consist of up to three identical alpha chains or a heterotypic molecule which is composed of three genetically distinct alpha chains. Alpha chains are identified in the format $\alpha(N)$, where n is the number of the chain and N is the collagen type. Therefore, collagen I which is a heterotrimer with two alpha one chains and one alpha two chain is represented as $\alpha 1(I)_2 \alpha 2(I)$ [Fratzl, 2008].

Each alpha chain has the structure of a left-handed helix; the three helices are twisted together to give a right-handed triple helical structure. This is a necessary but not a sufficient condition for a collagen molecule. This right-handed triple helix has a quaternary structure which is stabilized by hydrogen bonds. Glycine being the smallest amino acid is required at every third position, the structure of the triple helix puts this residue at the interior as there is only space for glycine's single hydrogen atom. Additionally, the rings of proline and hydroxyproline must point outward which helps stabilize the triple helix [Fratzl, 2008]. A single collagen molecule is known as tropocollagen and many tropocollagen molecules can form together to make up larger collagen aggregates, such as fibrils which form the tissue in tendons.

1.1.1 Formation of Fibrils

Fibrillar collagens are one type out of 28 different proteins classified as collagens and can form collagen fibrils. Fibrillar collagens include types I, II and III, they have the common characteristic of a long central triple-helical region in each alpha chain. This region is bordered by short non-helical regions called telopeptides.

The formation of fibrils is complex and involves intra-cellular and extra-cellular processes, both are necessary for the shaping of the structural and biomechanical properties of the fibril. It starts in the ribosome of the cell where the procollagen alpha chains are synthesized (all fibrillar collagens are synthesized from a soluble precursor molecule called procollagen). In the rough endoplasmic reticulum, the procollagen is then synthesized to form the triple helix structure. The molecules then move to the Golgi network and are packed into secretory vesicles and exported into the extracellular matrix. The extracellular matrix provides structural support to cells and is essentially the scaffolding between muscle and bone. Lastly, the fibrils are then stabilized by the formation of covalent cross-links [Fratzl, 2008].

The defining characteristic of collagen fibrils is a repeating band pattern with a so-called D periodicity of 64-67nm. Collagen molecules of length 300nm and width 1.5nm are staggered in the fibril by multiples of D also [Fratzl, 2008], as illustrated in the Figure 1.1 below.

Figure 1.1: The arrangement of collagen molecules in a fibril. Diagram adapted from [Hulmes, 2008].

1.1.2 Fibril Crimping

It is widely reported that collagen fibrils are not straight but wavy in shape. This is because in fibrils the collagen molecules are tilted with respect to the fibril axis. As discussed by Kastelic et al. [Kastelic et al., 1980] in an article titled ‘A structural mechanical model for tendon crimping’, it is suggested for simplicity, that the wave structure can be modelled as a crimp rather than a sinusoidal wave. A diagram of a crimp is shown in Figure 1.2. This crimp structure is displayed in tendons for all animals in addition to other collagenous tissues and is modelled through crimp angle and crimp period as illustrated in Figure 1.2. Crimping allows small longitudinal stretching of fibrils without damaging them, providing a level of protection to the tendon against small tensile strains. When a fascicle or tendon is observed through polarized light microscopy, the wavy arrangement of the fibrils is made clear through distinctive periodic light and dark bands [Franchi et al., 2007]. An unstrained Achilles tendon under polarized light can be seen in Figure 1.3. The fibrils can ‘uncrimp’ when the tendon is

subjected to tension and the wavy structure is straightened out.

Figure 1.2: The crimp structure of a collagen fibril displaying the crimp angle θ and crimp period. If stretched θ decreases as the period increases. L represents the length and β is a blunting factor which is necessary if the crimp is modelled as a pointed triangle rather than a sinusoidal wave.

Figure 1.3: An unstrained Achilles tendon under polarized light, observe the distinctive light and dark bands. Image taken from [Whittaker and Canham, 1991].

1.2 Tendon Structure

A tendon is composed of collagen fibrils densely packed in an amorphous ground substance which includes mostly water with collagen making up 65% – 86% of the dry weight. They are well-organized hierarchical structures. Five tropocollagen molecules make up a microfibril, microfibrils are the entities which make up fibrils. Fibrils are bunched in groups called fibres to form fascicles which themselves are bundled together and surrounded by the epitenon to form the tendon [Buschmann and Burgisser, 2017]. This is illustrated in figure 1.4. Fibrils can form strong chemical bonds with adjacent fibrils allowing them to group together, through cross-linking. Divalent and trivalent enzymatic cross-links form during the development of collagen fibrils which stiffen the fibrils by resisting intermolecular sliding [Eekhoff et al., 2018]. The typical size of a fascicle can vary, this variation accounts for each tendon in the body being specifically tailored to its role. An example of this is how tendons can be rounded cords or flattened bands [Benjamin and Ralphs, 1997]. Additionally, in the body of the tendon, there exists a small percentage of collagen molecules which are arranged horizontally, diagonally and helically. This ensures there is a buffer against non-longitudinal forces such as twisting and lateral loading

[Kannus, 2000].

Figure 1.4: The hierarchical structure of a typical tendon. Image taken from [Koh et al., 2021].

1.2.1 Additional Components of the Tendon

As mentioned earlier the tendon is composed of mostly collagen, but there are additional components that make up the tendon which is important to note when investigating its mechanical properties. In the tendon, 1-2% of the dry mass consists of elastin. Elastin is an extracellular protein which makes up the elastic fibres which are an important component of the extracellular matrix. The function of the elastic fibres is not well understood however, it is thought that they may help with the recoiling properties of fibrils when they return to their crimped state post stretch [Kannus, 2000]. Additionally proteoglycans exist in the fibrils. Proteoglycans are negatively charged macromolecules that can hold water fifty times their weight, this water-binding capacity improves the elasticity of the tendon. Proteoglycans are stiff¹ due to their high charge density and mutual repulsion, which allows the fibrils to resist high compressive and tensile forces [Kannus, 2000].

1.3 Material Behaviour

In the previous section, I laid out the biological structure of the tendon and showed that collagen is the most important component of tendon behaviour. To understand the properties of tendons in a more mathematically precise way and model their mechanics, key mechanical concepts must be introduced. In this section, the concepts of stress, strain, stiffness, strength, toughness, elasticity, viscoelasticity and plasticity shall be introduced. The definitions are only introduced in one dimension as in this project when modelling a tendon, I am only concerned with the response when the tendon is subjected to a lateral force. Therefore there will only be deformation in one direction.

¹See below for a formal definition of stiffness

1.3.1 Stress

Stress is a physical quantity that describes the magnitude of forces that cause deformation. It is defined as force per unit area. The stress σ can be described as

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A}, \quad (1.1)$$

where F is the force and A is the cross-sectional area of the material. In Standard International units, stress is measured in newtons per square meter (N/m^2) or pascals (Pa), where 1 MPa is equivalent to 1 million pascals which is equal to $1 N/mm^2$.

1.3.2 Strain

Strain is caused by a force and it need not be an applied one, for example, thermal strain occurs if an object is heated. If a strain is due to an applied force it is called mechanical strain. Strain is used as a general term for an elongation process as well as a shortening process where the former is a positive strain and the latter is negative [Hoffman, 1989]. Strain is the deformation of a material due to the material being subjected to applied stress. If ε is the strain measure then

$$\varepsilon = \frac{L - L_0}{L_0}, \quad (1.2)$$

where L_0 is the original length of material which is stretched to a length L . $\frac{L}{L_0}$ is called the stretch ratio. Normally when elongation occurs it leads to a contraction in the opposite direction to the applied stress. This is a relative amount and is represented by $\nu\varepsilon$ where ν is called Poisson's ratio.

1.3.3 Stiffness, Strength and Toughness

Young's modulus describes the stiffness of a material. Stiffness is the resistance against deformation when a material is subjected to a given stress [Fratzl, 2008]. Tendons are considered stiff materials relative to other soft tissues, and their property of stiffness is important in transmitting forces.

The strength of a material is the maximum stress the material can sustain before it breaks. Tendons must be strong as they need to be able to endure high loads without breakage [Fratzl, 2008].

Additionally, the toughness of a material can be described as the minimum energy needed to create a crack through the material so that it breaks. Brittle materials are not tough but can be stiff. Many materials that deform easily are also tough as deformation allows the material to dissipate energy rather than break. Toughness can be measured by calculating the area under a stress-strain curve when a material is loaded until failure. It can be measured in J/m^3 as it represents the energy per unit volume needed for breakage [Fratzl, 2008].

To recap, a stiff material needs a large force to deform, a strong material needs a large force to break and a tough material needs large energy to break. Compared to other soft tissues tendons are considered stiff, strong and tough.

1.3.4 A Typical Tendon Stress-Strain Curve

The tendon's unique hierarchical structure and composition give rise to characteristic mechanical behaviour which can be seen in a stress-strain curve. Typically, the stress-strain curve can be viewed in four distinct regions, the first being the toe region. In this region the crimped tendon fibrils are being 'stretched out' due to mechanical loading, this mechanical property can vary from tendon to tendon

depending on its location and type. Different tendons have various wavy fibril patterns, therefore the initial mechanical properties of the tendon vary as the angle and length of the crimping vary. On a tendon stress-strain curve, this can change the shape of the curve in the ‘toe’ region which is shown in Figure 1.5.

After the toe region, there is a linear region, in this region the crimp pattern is lost and the fibrils become orientated in the same direction as the mechanical load. The gradient of the linear slope is often referred to as the Young’s modulus of the tendon.

If the strain continues to increase microscopic tearing of the tendon will begin to occur causing microtear failure. If the strain increases further macroscopic tearing occurs which will eventually lead to tendon rupture [Wang, 2006].

It should be noted that different tendons have different mechanical properties, which is due to varying tendon functions. An example of this is that the Young’s Modulus of the human patella tendon between the ages of 29-50 years, is $600 \pm 266\text{MPa}$ whilst the human tibialis anterior Young’s modulus is 1200MPa . Age also affects mechanical properties, which is demonstrated in the following example, a human patella tendon aged 64-93 years was recorded to have a Young’s Modulus of $504 \pm 222\text{MPa}$ [Wang, 2006] which is significantly lower for a 29-50-year-old patellar tendon.

Figure 1.5: Stress-Strain curve of a tendon. Image taken from [Wang, 2006]

1.3.5 Elasticity, Plasticity and Viscoelasticity

The mechanical properties of elasticity, plasticity and viscoelasticity can be discovered by exploring the relationship between stress and strain.

Elasticity

A material is said to display elastic behaviour if it returns to its original shape and size when the forces causing deformation are removed, thus a relationship between stress and strain is maintained.

For linear elastic materials, the ratio between stress and strain is called Young's modulus with the linear relationship $\sigma = E\varepsilon$. This is demonstrated in Figure 1.6 (i). It is more common for biological soft tissues to display non-linear elastic behaviour [Fratzl, 2008]. Non-linear elasticity occurs when the stress-strain graph does not display a linear relationship (Figure 1.6 (ii)).

Plasticity

Once the stress has reached yield stress for a material it will not return to its original shape so does not display elastic behaviour but rather plastic behaviour [Fratzl, 2008]. When a material is subjected to stress at this critical point it undergoes a deformation known as permanent strain, denoted ε_p , which is the associated plastic deformation. This deformation is visible in the stress-strain curve in Figure 1.6 (iii) where the dashed line does not cross the origin. The distance from the origin and the x-intercept of the dashed line correspond to the permanent strain. Tendons can exhibit plastic behaviour in response to mechanical loading and damage to the tendon has been shown to occur post static and cyclic mechanical loading [Arampatzis et al., 2009].

Viscoelasticity

Viscoelasticity is when the material will slowly return to its original shape after being subjected to stress [Fratzl, 2008]. Viscoelasticity is a time-dependent mechanical behaviour in which viscoelastic materials exhibit both viscous and elastic behaviour, as tendons are viscoelastic they display both these mechanical behaviours. Viscosity is the measure of resistance to deformation at a given rate. Figure 1.6 (iv) shows a typical stress-strain graph for a viscoelastic material, it can be seen that the loading and unloading curve does not follow the same path but a loop. This phenomenon is called hysteresis.

In a tendon, there are three important characteristics of viscoelasticity: creep, stress relaxation and hysteresis. Creep is a property that is used to describe increasing deformation under a constant load. Elastic materials in general do not elongate regardless of how long the load is applied. A viscoelastic material can undergo a creep test, this involves loading the material at constant stress and subjecting the material to the stress for a length of time. Figure 1.7 displays the typical response of a viscoelastic material subjected to a creep test.

Stress relaxation indicates that the stress acting on a tendon will reduce under a constant deformation (Figure 1.8). These results can be found by performing a stress relaxation test. This involves straining a viscoelastic material at a constant strain and holding the strain. The results show that the stress required to hold the material at the constant strain will decrease through time.

Finally, as mentioned previously hysteresis is a phenomenon used to describe a viscoelastic material which when loaded and unloaded has a different unloading and loading curve (Figure 1.6 (iv)). The difference between the loading and unloading curve represents the energy which is lost during loading. This energy is dissipated as heat due to internal friction. Under cyclic loading, the amount of hysteresis decreases as the material is continuously loaded and unloaded and stress-strain curves are reproducible. This is known as pseudo-elasticity and represents the non-linearity of tendon stress-strain behaviour [Robi et al., 2013].

Figure 1.6: The loading and unloading curves for linear elastic, non-linear elastic, plastic and viscoelastic materials. The solid lines represent the loading curves and the dotted lines represent the unloading curves. Image taken from [Wang and Pierscionek, 2019].

1.4 Introducing the Collagen Recruitment Model

1.4.1 Sequential Straightening and Loading

Diamant et al [Diamant et al., 1972] have conducted experiments to conclude that the crimp structure of fibrils is affected when a tendon deforms. They found that the wave-like structure is straightened out as the tendon is stretched. The fibrils then return to their crimping structure post deformation, exhibiting recoiling properties giving the tendon elasticity [Franchi et al., 2010]. The phenomenon of uncrimping of the collagen fibrils can be described by the sequential strengthening and loading (SSL) model formulated by Kastelic, Palley and Baer [Kastelic et al., 1980]. This model makes a few notable assumptions, namely, the fibrils do not all exhibit the same crimp pattern i.e. there is a variation in crimp angle throughout the fibrils in an undeformed tendon. The model also only considers exerted resistance from the taut fibrils assuming that there is no resistance from the crimped fibrils. Finally, as illustrated in Figure 1.2 the wave shape is modelled as a triangular point rather than a sinusoidal wave which would be more reflective of reality. To account for this the SSL introduces the parameter β which represents a crimp blunting factor.

1.4.2 The Collagen Recruitment Model

The collagen recruitment model developed by Lanir [Lanir, 1983] is based on the same assumptions as the SSL model however, it also takes into consideration that the waviness of the fibrils is nonuniform [Lanir, 1983]. The recruitment model maintains that under a uniaxial stretch there is gradual recruitment of the fibrils due to individual differences in their extended lengths [Viidik and Ekholm, 1968]. This is because the wavy structure of the fibrils is not identical and varies from fibril to fibril. The

Figure 1.7: Creep is increasing deformation under a constant load. Image taken from [?]

Figure 1.8: Stress relaxation - stress is reduced under a constant deformation. Image taken from [?]

fibre is modelled as a two-phase inhomogeneous medium made up of the viscoelastic extracollagenous matrix and the viscoelastic fibrils [Shearer et al., 2020]. When subjected to deformation the fibrils stretch as the matrix expels the fluid in between the fibrils causing their movement [Lanir, 1983]. This suggests that the macroscopic response of the fibre is a result of the micromechanical behaviour of the fibrils that make it up. When the fibre is stretched naturally, it is the shortest fibrils that are first to become taut, as the stretch increases more fibrils become taut and the stiffness of the fibre increases [Shearer et al., 2020]. Lanir’s model makes the following assumptions: all the fibres are thin and perfectly flexible, and they have no compressive strength and will buckle if compressed under zero load. Hydrostatic pressure is the result of the matrix flow in deformation, the flow then stops when the intermolecular forces counteract the pressure. Finally, each fibre is subjected to a uniaxial strain which is a tensorial transformation of the overall strain in the fibril’s direction [Lanir, 1983]. This is essentially just a transformation of the overall strain under a coordinate change. Both the fibrils and the matrix can be modelled as linear viscoelastic as the model assumes a variety of different fibril lengths.

We now have a enough knowledge about the biological background of the tendon to understand how significant the structure of a tendon is, in it’s material response to strain. Additionally, key mechanical definitions have been introduced which will be necessary in describing the tendon’s mechanical response later on.

Chapter 2

Linear Viscoelastic Constitutive Models

Before I lay out the mathematics behind the collagen recruitment model, I shall introduce the concept of viscoelastic constitutive models. These models which include the Maxwell model, the Kelvin-Voigt model and the Standard linear solid model are used to investigate a viscoelastic solid's response under different loading conditions. It is important to introduce these models as we can compare the results of the creep-recovery test and the stress-relaxation test, with results produced by a tendon subjected to the same tests. By comparison, it is possible to conclude which constitutive model would be best when modelling the viscoelastic properties of a tendon. Once this is decided, the constitutive equation for the most suitable model can be manipulated by transformations and rearranged until it can be compared to the collagen recruitment model. Upon comparison, it is possible to determine the expression which models viscoelasticity and include this in the collagen recruitment model, so that when modelling the material properties of a tendon, viscoelasticity can be assumed.

2.1 Introduction to Rheological Models

To simulate the stress-strain behaviour of viscoelastic materials, models composed of springs and dash-pots are used. These models are known as rheological models or mechanical models. Rheological models can be represented as electrical circuits where stress is represented by voltage and the rate of strain by the current. We can then compare the stress-strain curves of tendons obtained by experimental data to the circuits to decide if they accurately describe the viscoelastic properties of the tendon.

2.1.1 The Spring

The elastic component of the viscoelastic material is modelled as a spring (Figure 2.1), this has the constitutive equation

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{E}\sigma, \quad (2.1)$$

where E represents the stiffness of the material (or Young's modulus). If subjected to a creep-recovery test¹ the material would undergo an instantaneous elastic strain when loaded, maintain the strain whilst the load is applied and then instantaneously de-strain with the removal of the load (Figure 2.2).

¹A creep-recovery test is similar to a creep test, the difference being the material behaviour is also observed under de-straining when the load is removed.

Figure 2.1: The linear elastic spring. Image taken from [Kelly, 2013].

When modelling the response from a creep-recovery test it is required to model the stress condition in terms of the Heaviside function²

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 \mathcal{H}(t) - \sigma_0 \mathcal{H}(t - T). \quad (2.2)$$

Where the derivative is

$$\dot{\sigma}(t) = \sigma_0 \delta(t) - \sigma_0 \delta(t - T). \quad (2.3)$$

Note that the Dirac delta function³, $\delta(t)$, is the derivative of the Heaviside function.

Figure 2.2: Creep-recovery response of a spring.

2.1.2 The Dash-Pot

The viscous component of the material is modelled by a dash-pot (Figure 2.3), a dash-pot is a piston-cylinder arrangement which is filled with viscous fluid. When the piston is pushed through the fluid a strain is achieved. The dash-pot displays a strain rate proportional to stress

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{1}{\eta} \sigma, \quad (2.4)$$

where η is the viscosity. This is the typical response for a lot of fluids, increasing the stress means a quicker straining. To find the strain due to an applied load σ_0 , one can integrate equation (2.2) with

²See appendix for a formal definition of the Heaviside function.

³See the appendix for a formal definition of the Dirac delta function.

Figure 2.3: The linear dash-pot. Image taken from [Kelly, 2013].

respect to time t . Here we have assumed the function $\sigma(t)$ takes the form of a constant σ_0 and there is zero initial strain. Therefore, we are left with

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma_0}{\eta}t, \quad (2.5)$$

showing the strain to increase linearly and becoming unbounded when stress is applied. This is displayed in Figure 2.4, it can be seen that upon loading it takes time for the strain to increase but once the load is removed there is no stress to move the piston back through the fluid. The gradient of

Figure 2.4: Stress condition and the creep-recovery response of the dash-pot. Image taken from [Kelly, 2013].

the creep line is $\frac{\sigma_0}{\eta}$ and the relationship between the stress and strain is

$$\varepsilon(t) = \sigma_0 J(t), \quad (2.6)$$

where J is the creep (compliance) function ⁴.

2.2 The Maxwell Model

A spring and a dash-pot in series is known as the Maxwell model (Figure 2.5). The total strain for the system can be split into the spring strain ε_S and the dash-pot strain ε_D , for equilibrium it requires that the stress be the same in each element. We can now derive the constitutive equation from the

⁴ $J = \frac{1}{E}$ for an elastic spring

mathematical expressions for spring and dash-pot strain.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varepsilon &= \varepsilon_S + \varepsilon_D. \\
 \dot{\varepsilon} &= \dot{\varepsilon}_S + \dot{\varepsilon}_D. \\
 \dot{\varepsilon} &= \frac{\sigma}{\eta} + \frac{1}{E}\dot{\sigma}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.7}$$

Now we have a constitutive equation for the Maxwell model which relates stress to strain and we can investigate how the model behaves under applied stress or strain.

Figure 2.5: The Maxwell model. Image taken from [Cole, 2017].

2.2.1 Creep-Recovery Response

If subjected to a creep-recovery test, the Maxwell model is exposed to a stress σ_0 and the spring will stretch instantaneously whilst the dash-pot will take time to react. This means the initial strain is $\varepsilon(0) = \frac{\sigma_0}{E}$. Having substituted the stress condition displayed in Figure 2.4 into the constitutive equation in terms of the Heaviside function, you can combine and integrate these equations to give the strain response

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{\varepsilon}(t) &= \frac{\sigma_0}{\eta}(\mathcal{H}(t) - \mathcal{H}(t - T)) + \frac{\sigma_0}{E}(\delta\mathcal{H}(t) - \delta(t - T)). \\
 \varepsilon(t) &= \frac{\sigma_0}{\eta}(t\mathcal{H}(t) + (T - t)\mathcal{H}(t - T)) + \frac{\sigma_0}{E}(\mathcal{H}(t) - \mathcal{H}(t - T)).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.8}$$

This can be represented in the form

$$\varepsilon(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t < 0, \\ \frac{\sigma_0}{\eta}t + \frac{\sigma_0}{E} & 0 \leq t < T, \\ \frac{\sigma_0}{\eta}T & T \leq t. \end{cases}
 \tag{2.9}$$

When the load is removed the spring recoils immediately but the dash-pot will not recover, therefore the strain will immediately decrease by $\varepsilon(0) = \frac{\sigma_0}{E}$ which is equal to the originally applied strain. The creep-recovery response is illustrated in Figure 2.6.

Upon inspection of Figure 2.6, once the load is applied, there is an instantaneous stretch from the spring of $\varepsilon(0) = \frac{\sigma_0}{E}$. This is the linear creep response. After unloading the graph suggests permanent deformation.

Figure 2.6: The creep-recovery response for the Maxwell model. The formula for the graph comes from equation 2.8. Image taken from [Kelly, 2013].

With regards to the tendon this model does not seem like a good fit, Oza et al. [Oza et al., 2006] showed that the tendon's creep response was non-linear, with the rate of strain decreasing with time, a contradiction to the Maxwell model. Also, when modelling tendon viscoelasticity it does not seem physically accurate to suggest a permanent deformation after unloading, as this is a property of a viscoelastic fluid rather than a solid. Therefore, it can be concluded that with respect to creep, the Maxwell model is not adequate in modelling tendon viscoelastic properties.

2.2.2 Stress-Relaxation Response

Investigating the stress-relaxation of the Maxwell model will provide information about the reaction of stress whilst under a strain condition. Substituting the following step condition

$$\varepsilon(t) = \varepsilon_0 \mathcal{H}(t) - \varepsilon_0 \mathcal{H}(t - T). \quad (2.10)$$

into the constitutive equation (2.7) we obtain

$$\varepsilon_0 \delta(t) - \varepsilon_0 \delta(t - T) = \frac{\sigma}{\eta} + \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{E}. \quad (2.11)$$

This equation can be solved by the use of the Laplace transform⁵ where $\mathcal{L}\{\delta(t)\} \rightarrow 1$ and $\mathcal{L}\{\delta(t - T)\} \rightarrow e^{-sT}$. This gives

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_0 e^{-sT} &= \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\eta} + \frac{s\bar{\sigma}}{E}, \\ \bar{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{\eta} + \frac{s}{E} \right) &= \varepsilon_0 (1 - e^{-sT}), \\ \bar{\sigma}(s) &= \varepsilon_0 E \left(\frac{1}{\frac{E}{\eta} + s} - \frac{e^{-sT}}{\frac{E}{\eta} + s} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

⁵The Laplace transform can also be found in the appendix, additionally there are several Laplace transforms which provide us with useful results used in this project.

when we rearranged to make $\bar{\sigma}$ the subject. To determine $\sigma(t)$ from $\bar{\sigma}$, the inverse Laplace transform is used to give

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(t) &= \varepsilon_0 E \left(e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}t} - e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}(t-T)} \mathcal{H}(t-T) \right), \\ \sigma(t) &= \varepsilon_0 E e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}t} \left(1 - e^{\frac{E}{\eta}T} \mathcal{H}(t-T) \right).\end{aligned}\tag{2.13}$$

This can be represented as

$$\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t \leq 0, \\ \varepsilon_0 E e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}t} & 0 \leq t < T, \\ \varepsilon_0 E e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}t} \left(1 - e^{\frac{E}{\eta}T} \right) & T \leq t. \end{cases}\tag{2.14}$$

This is illustrated in Figure 2.7, it can be seen that at the loading time of $t = 0$, the stress instantaneously increases and then decreases over time. When the load is removed at $t = T$, there is an instant decrease in stress and a reserve relaxation. The stress-relaxation of the Maxwell model can be

Figure 2.7: The stress-recovery response for the Maxwell model, the formula for the graph comes from equation 2.14. Image taken from (Cole 2017)

defined as $\sigma(t) = G(t)\varepsilon_0$, where $G(t) = E e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}t} \left(1 - e^{\frac{E}{\eta}T} \mathcal{H}(t-T) \right)$ is the relaxation response of the constitutive equation. The Maxwell model predicts that the stress will decay exponentially with time, which is accurate for the tendon. However it also implies that as $t \rightarrow \infty$, the stress would go to zero, this is not a property of viscoelastic solids but common in viscoelastic fluids.

2.3 The Kelvin-Voigt Model

Consider now the Kelvin-Voigt model, which is a spring and dash-pot in parallel (Figure 2.8), we assume there is no bending in the arrangement so that the spring and dash-pot experience the same strain. We can derive the constitutive equation from the mathematical expressions for spring and dash-pot stress. Recall the constitutive equation for the spring is $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{E}\sigma$ and the dash-pot is $\dot{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{\eta}\sigma$. Writing the overall stress as the stress of the spring, plus the stress of the dash-pot and eliminating σ_S and σ_D gives

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma &= \sigma_S + \sigma_D, \\ \sigma &= E\varepsilon + \eta\dot{\varepsilon},\end{aligned}\tag{2.15}$$

Figure 2.8: The Kelvin-Voigt Model. Image taken from (Kelly 2013).

which leaves the constitutive law for the Kelvin-Voigt Model.

2.3.1 Creep-Recovery Response

If a load σ_0 is applied to the Kelvin-Voigt model the spring will not be able to instantaneously stretch as the dash-pot is restricting the overall strain. Therefore, the stress is initially taken by the dash-pot and the creep curve has an initial slope starting at $\frac{\sigma_0}{\eta}$.

As time increases strain begins to occur, allowing stress to be transferred from the dash-pot to the spring. The gradient of the creep curve becomes $\frac{\sigma_D}{\eta}$ where σ_D is the dashpot-stress which is decreasing to zero.

Solving equation 2.15 as a first order non-homogeneous differential equation with the initial condition $\varepsilon(0) = 0$, gives the solution

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\sigma_0}{\eta} \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{E}{\eta}\right)t} \right). \quad (2.16)$$

The creep compliance function for the Kelvin-Voigt model is

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{E} \left(1 - e^{-t/t_R} \right), \quad t_R = \frac{\eta}{E}. \quad (2.17)$$

Here the parameter t_R , represents the retardation time which measures the time taken for the creep strain to accumulate.

Upon unloading the Kelvin-Voigt model, the dash-pot will prevent the spring from immediately contracting, it will instead pull the dash-pot to its original position over time until full recovery.

Consider the time of unloading at $t = T$. At stress equal to zero, the constitutive law (equation 2.15) becomes $0 = E\varepsilon + \eta\dot{\varepsilon}$ which upon solving leads to

$$\varepsilon(t) = C e^{-\left(\frac{E}{\eta}\right)t}, \quad (2.18)$$

where C is a constant of integration. If you were to measure the time from the position of loading, t should be replaced by $t - T$.

Using the condition $t = T$ in equation 2.16 leaves

$$\varepsilon(T) = \frac{\sigma_0}{E} \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{E}{\eta}\right)T} \right), \quad (2.19)$$

which can be used as the initial condition to solve the value of C. This leads to the solution

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\sigma_0}{E} e^{-\left(\frac{E}{\eta}\right)t} \left(e^{\left(\frac{E}{\eta}\right)T} - 1 \right), \quad t > T, \quad (2.20)$$

which can be represented as

$$\varepsilon(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_0}{E} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}t}\right) & 0 \leq t < T, \\ \frac{\sigma_0}{E} \left(e^{\frac{E}{\eta}T} - 1\right) e^{-\frac{E}{\eta}t} & t > T. \end{cases} \quad (2.21)$$

This result is shown in Figure 2.9, where a reverse creep response can be seen when the load is removed. At $t = 0$, the strain is 0, this represents the spring being unable to react immediately due to the stretching by the dash-pot. It would appear that this is a more accurate representation of the creep response for a tendon than the Maxwell model can produce, as a tendon's creep response is non-linear with the rate of strain decreasing with time. Unlike the Maxwell model, when the load is removed, rather than exhibiting deformation, the Kelvin-Voigt model displays the viscoelastic property of returning to the original shape at a rate dependent on time.

Figure 2.9: The creep-recovery response for the Kelvin-Voigt Model. Image taken from (Cole 2017).

2.3.2 Stress-Relaxation Response

Consider now the stress-relaxation test, which investigates the stress response to the strain condition. Combining the step condition (2.10) used in the Maxwell model, into the constitutive equation (2.15) leaves us with

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon_0\mathcal{H}(t) - E\varepsilon_0\mathcal{H}(t - T) + \eta\varepsilon_0\delta(t) - \eta\varepsilon_0\delta(t - T) \quad (2.22)$$

This particular equation describes the stress response at differing values of t . Upon inspection, it can be determined that for differing values of t the stress takes the values of

$$\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & t < 0, \\ \eta\varepsilon_0\delta(t) & t = 0, \\ E\varepsilon_0 & 0 < t < T, \\ -\eta\varepsilon_0\delta(t - T) & t = T, \\ 0 & T < t. \end{cases} \quad (2.23)$$

Notice that in the range $0 < t < T$, $\sigma = E\varepsilon_0$ where ε_0 is a constant. This means that the stress taken up by the spring is constant, thus there is no stress-relaxation over time. For the Kelvin-Voigt model

to undergo an instantaneous strain of ε_0 , infinite stress must be applied. This can be seen at the values of $t = 0$, and $t = T$, where $\delta(0)$ will emerge. This implies that the stress response at these times is of infinite magnitude. This phenomenon can be explained by treating the strain as a double-step function which jumps from 0 to ε_0 instantly, suggesting the rate of strain at $t = 0$, and $t = T$ is infinite. Clearly, this is not an accurate model to use when investigating the stress-relaxation of the tendon, as it is physically impossible to produce these results in real life.

2.4 The Standard Linear Solid Model

I have introduced the Maxwell and Kelvin-Voigt models which are the simplest models used to model viscoelastic behaviour. Whilst these models are useful in displaying some of the behaviour of viscoelastic tendons, I have shown how they have inaccuracies. In particular, whilst the Maxwell model can produce results in the stress-relaxation test that reflect tendon stress-relaxation, the results in the creep test are inaccurate in describing tendon creep. In contrast, the Kelvin-Voigt model, when subjected to a creep test produces results that align with the creep response of the tendon. However, the results from the stress-relaxation test are physically impossible in real life.

To create more realistic material responses from rheological models, one can introduce more elements to the circuit. The standard linear solid models for solids are a combination of the Kelvin-Voigt model and the Maxwell model. One can have the Kelvin-Voigt model in series with a spring or the Maxwell model in parallel with a spring. These arrangements are displayed in Figure 2.10, when subjected to the creep and stress-relaxation test both models are equivalent. I shall derive the stress-strain relation using the former which is the first diagram in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10: Two representations of a Standard Linear solid model. The first is a spring in series with the Kelvin-Voigt model and the second is a spring in parallel with the Maxwell model. Image adapted from [Kelly, 2013].

As in the Maxwell and Kelvin-Voigt models, we can split the overall stress and strain into linear

combinations which correspond to the springs and dash-pots as so,

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma &= \sigma_1 + \sigma_2, \\ \varepsilon &= \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2,\end{aligned}\tag{2.24}$$

where

$$\sigma = E_1\varepsilon_1, \quad \sigma_1 = E_2\varepsilon_2, \quad \sigma_2 = \eta\dot{\varepsilon}_2.\tag{2.25}$$

To combine these equations, you can transform them via the Laplace transform to simplify the differential term. Once transformed the equations are

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\sigma} &= \bar{\sigma}_1 + \bar{\sigma}_2, \\ \bar{\varepsilon} &= \bar{\varepsilon}_1 + \bar{\varepsilon}_2,\end{aligned}\tag{2.26}$$

where

$$\bar{\sigma} = E_1\bar{\varepsilon}_1, \quad \bar{\sigma}_1 = E_2\bar{\varepsilon}_2, \quad \bar{\sigma}_2 = \eta s\bar{\varepsilon}_2.\tag{2.27}$$

We can combine and substitute these equations into each other to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\sigma}_2 &= E_2\bar{\varepsilon}_2, \\ \bar{\sigma} - \eta s\bar{\varepsilon}_2 &= E_2\bar{\varepsilon}_2, \\ (E_2 + \eta s)\bar{\varepsilon}_2 &= \bar{\sigma}, \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_2 &= \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{(E_2 + \eta s)}, \\ \bar{\sigma} &= E_1(\bar{\varepsilon} - \bar{\varepsilon}_2), \\ \bar{\sigma} &= E_1\left(\bar{\varepsilon} - \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{E_2 + \eta s}\right), \\ (E_2 + E_1)\bar{\sigma} + \eta s\bar{\sigma} &= E_1E_2\bar{\varepsilon} + E_1\eta s\bar{\varepsilon}, \\ \bar{\sigma} + \frac{\eta s}{E_1 + E_2}\bar{\sigma} &= \frac{E_1E_2}{E_1 + E_2}\bar{\varepsilon} + \frac{E_1\eta s}{E_1 + E_2}\bar{\varepsilon}.\end{aligned}\tag{2.28}$$

Transforming back to the original notation by the inverse Laplace transform we arrive at the desired result, which represents the stress-strain relationship,

$$\sigma + \frac{\eta}{E_1 + E_2}\dot{\sigma} = \frac{E_1E_2}{E_1 + E_2}\varepsilon + \frac{E_1\eta}{E_1 + E_2}\dot{\varepsilon}.\tag{2.29}$$

2.4.1 Creep-Recovery Response

Once again as we did for the Maxwell model, we substitute the stress condition in terms of the Heaviside function into the stress-strain relation (2.29) for the Standard Liner model. This gives

$$\begin{aligned}(E_1E_2\varepsilon + E_1\eta s)\frac{\bar{\varepsilon}}{\sigma_0} &= (E_1 + E_2)\left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{e^{-sT}}{s}\right) + \eta(1 - e^{-sT}), \\ \left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s\right)E_1\eta\frac{\bar{\varepsilon}}{\sigma_0} &= (E_1 + E_2)\left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{e^{-sT}}{s}\right) + \eta(1 - e^{-sT}).\end{aligned}\tag{2.30}$$

We can now use the Laplace transform to transform the equation to obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
(E_1 E_2 \varepsilon + E_1 \eta s) \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}}{\sigma_0} &= (E_1 + E_2) \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{e^{-sT}}{s} \right) + \eta (1 - e^{-sT}), \\
\left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s \right) E_1 \eta \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}}{\sigma_0} &= (E_1 + E_2) \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{e^{-sT}}{s} \right) + \eta (1 - e^{-sT}), \\
E_1 \eta \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}}{\sigma_0} &= (E_1 + E_2) \cdot \frac{1}{s \left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s \right)} - (E_1 + E_2) \cdot \frac{e^{-sT}}{s \left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s \right)} + \frac{\eta}{\left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s \right)} - \frac{\eta e^{-sT}}{\left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s \right)}.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.31}$$

Using the inverse Laplace transform, this equation can be transformed back into the original notation which considers a time variable. The $\frac{e^{-sT}}{s \left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s \right)}$ term can be dealt with by using the Convolution Theorem⁶ where

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{e^{-sT}}{s \left(\frac{E_2}{\eta} + s \right)} \right\} \rightarrow \int_0^t \delta((t-T) - \tau) \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta} \tau}}{\frac{E_2}{\eta}} d\tau. \tag{2.32}$$

At time $t = T$, when $t > T$, the Dirac delta function allows the integral to be equal to itself, this allows us to write it in terms of the Heaviside function,

$$\frac{1 - e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta}(t-T)}}{\frac{E_2}{\eta}} \mathcal{H}(t-T). \tag{2.33}$$

Subsequently, equation (2.31) once transformed under the inverse Laplace transform, can be written as

$$\frac{\varepsilon(t)}{\sigma_0} = \frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1 \eta} \left[\frac{1 - e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta} t}}{\frac{E_2}{\eta}} - \frac{1 - e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta}(t-T)}}{\frac{E_2}{\eta}} \mathcal{H}(t-T) \right] + \frac{1}{E_1} \left[e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta} t} - e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta}(t-T)} \mathcal{H}(t-T) \right]. \tag{2.34}$$

When considering the strain before and after unloading at $t = T$, this can be written as

$$\varepsilon(t) = \begin{cases} \sigma_0 \left(\left(\frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1 E_2} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{E_1} - \frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1 E_2} \right) e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta} t} \right) & t < T, \\ \sigma_0 \left(\left(\frac{1}{E_1} - \frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1 E_2} \right) e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta} t} \left(\frac{1}{E_1} - \frac{E_1 + E_2}{E_1 E_2} \right) e^{-\frac{E_2}{\eta}(t-T)} \right) & t \geq T. \end{cases} \tag{2.35}$$

This result is shown in Figure 2.11, it is noticeably similar to the creep-recovery result for the Kelvin-Voigt model as desired. The difference is, when loaded there is an instant strain response, this is because there is a spring in series. This can be seen at $t = 0$ on the graph, where $\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma_0}{E_1}$ and E_1 is the spring constant for the spring in series. The dash-pot in the circuit prevents the second spring from contributing to the initial strain, explaining the shape of the graph when $t < T$. When unloaded the strain instantly decreases by $\varepsilon = \frac{\sigma_0}{E_1}$, before slowly decreasing until the original shape is returned.

2.4.2 Stress-Relaxation Response

Substituting the step condition (2.10), into the constitutive equation (2.29), allows us to determine the stress-relaxation response of the standard linear solid model. Upon substitution, we are left with

$$(E_1 + E_2) \sigma + \eta \dot{\sigma} = E_1 E_2 (\varepsilon_0 \mathcal{H}(t) - \varepsilon_0 \mathcal{H}(t-T)) + E_1 \eta (\varepsilon_0 \delta(t) - \varepsilon_0 \delta(t-T)), \tag{2.36}$$

⁶See appendix for a formal definition.

Figure 2.11: The creep-recovery response for the standard linear solid model for a solid. Image taken from [Cole, 2017].

which under a Laplace transformation, transforms to

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\varepsilon_0} (E_1 + E_2 + \eta s) = E_1 E_2 \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{s} e^{-sT} \right) + E_1 \eta (1 - e^{-sT}). \quad (2.37)$$

Setting $\lambda = \frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta}$ we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \eta \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\varepsilon_0} (\lambda + s) &= E_1 E_2 \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{s} e^{-sT} \right) + E_1 \eta (1 - e^{-sT}), \\ \eta \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\varepsilon_0} &= E_1 E_2 \left(\frac{1}{s(\lambda + s)} - \frac{e^{-sT}}{s(\lambda + s)} \right) + E_1 \eta \left(\frac{1}{\lambda + s} - \frac{e^{-sT}}{\lambda + s} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.38)$$

Once again we can change this equation back into the original notation by using the inverse Laplace transform. We use the convolution theorem to transform the $-\frac{e^{-sT}}{s(\lambda + s)}$ term, as it is a multiple of two inverse transforms. This gives

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{e^{-sT}}{s(\lambda + s)} \right\} \rightarrow \int_0^t \delta(t - T - \tau) \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda\tau}}{\lambda} d\tau, \quad (2.39)$$

where at time $t < T$, the Dirac delta function allows the integral to be equal to 0. This has an effect when $t > T$, the integral can now be written in terms of the Heaviside function

$$= \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda(t-T)}}{\lambda} \mathcal{H}(t - T). \quad (2.40)$$

Therefore once transformed back into the original notation which considers a time variable, we are left with

$$\eta \frac{\sigma(t)}{\varepsilon_0} = E_1 E_2 \left(\frac{1 - e^{-\lambda t}}{\lambda} - \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda(t-T)}}{\lambda} \mathcal{H}(t - T) \right) + E_1 \eta \left(e^{-\lambda t} - e^{-\lambda(t-T)} \mathcal{H}(t - T) \right). \quad (2.41)$$

Rewritten in separated form for $t < T$, and $t \geq T$, the stress response in terms of ε_0 and t is

$$\sigma(t) = \begin{cases} \varepsilon_0 \left(\frac{E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2} + \left(E_1 - \frac{E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2} \right) e^{-\frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta} t} \right) & t < T, \\ \varepsilon_0 \left(\left(E_1 - \frac{E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2} \right) e^{-\frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta} t} - \left(E_1 - \frac{E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2} \right) e^{-\frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta} (t-T)} \right) & t \geq T. \end{cases} \quad (2.42)$$

The graphical representation of this is displayed in Figure 2.12. It can be seen that between $0 < t < T$, when the strain is loaded there is an instantaneous response which then relaxes exponentially. If the strain was not removed this exponential relaxation would tend towards the positive value, $\frac{\varepsilon_0 E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2}$ which represents a property of viscoelastic solids. This is similar to the Maxwell model response but is a more accurate model for the tendon, as under an infinite strain the stress does not tend to zero but a positive value. When the strain is removed there is an instantaneous negative response and a relaxation response can be observed which tends to the original shape.

Figure 2.12: The stress-relaxation response of the standard linear solid model for a solid. Image taken from [Cole, 2017].

2.4.3 Generalized Models

It can be concluded that as the Standard-Linear model produces the most accurate results for the viscoelastic properties of a solid, the more elements the model has, the more accurate the model will be. However, in a more complex model, there will be more material parameters which must be experimentally evaluated which poses a difficulty [Kelly, 2013]. Normally, a more complex rheological model will be in the form of a generalized Maxwell model or a generalized Kelvin chain which is demonstrated in Figure 2.13.

When modelling a Generalized model, a differential equation is used. The more elements (springs/dashpots) the model has, the higher the order of the differential equation. In general, the constitutive equation will be in the form

$$p_0 \sigma + p_1 \dot{\sigma} + p_2 \ddot{\sigma} + p_3 \dddot{\sigma} + p_4 \sigma^{(IV)} + \dots = q_0 \varepsilon + q_1 \dot{\varepsilon} + q_2 \ddot{\varepsilon} + q_3 \dddot{\varepsilon} + q_4 \varepsilon^{(IV)} + \dots \quad (2.43)$$

Figure 2.13: Generalized viscoelastic models. Image taken from [Kelly, 2013].

This can be written as $\mathbf{P}\sigma = \mathbf{Q}\varepsilon$, where \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{Q} are the linear differential operators

$$\mathbf{P} = \sum_{i=0}^n p_i \frac{\partial^i}{\partial t^i}, \quad \mathbf{Q} = \sum_{i=0}^n q_i \frac{\partial^i}{\partial t^i}. \quad (2.44)$$

Therefore, by entering values for p_i and q_i , a viscoelastic model can be generated without the use of springs and dash-pots. Springs and dash-pots can be useful however, as they provide a physical model which can help our understanding of more complicated mathematical expressions such as 2.44.

By introducing and investigating various linear viscoelastic constitutive models and making comparisons between their responses to the creep-recovery and stress-relaxation tests, it can be concluded that the standard linear solid model is the most suitable for modelling the viscoelasticity of a fibril. This is because the results of the creep-recovery and stress-relaxation tests are most aligned with the behaviour of the fibril under the same tests. Now that this has been established, we will be able to substitute the constitutive equation for the standard linear solid model into the collagen recruitment model allowing us to model a tendon's behaviour under the assumption that it has viscoelastic properties. In the next chapter, I shall lay out the mathematics of the collagen recruitment model in detail. I will use my conclusions from this chapter and incorporate the derived constitutive equation from the standard linear solid model into the collagen recruitment model, ensuring the viscoelastic properties of the tendon are accounted for when investigating material behaviour.

Chapter 3

Mathematical Background for The Collagen Recruitment Model

As discussed in Section 1.4, the collagen recruitment model developed by Lanir [Lanir, 1983] is based on the SSL model. In the model developed by Shearer et al [Shearer et al., 2020] the matrix response is also taken into consideration due to the interactions between the fibrils within the matrix and the matrix itself, which causes viscosity. The total volume fraction of the fibrils is written as ϕ so the volume fraction of the matrix is $1 - \phi$ [Shearer et al., 2020].

The parameters used in the model are; $\sigma_f, \varepsilon_f, \sigma_m$ and ε_m , which represent the fibril stress and strain and the matrix stress and strain respectively. The imposed macroscopic fibre strain and stress are denoted by ε and σ .

3.1 Matrix Response

Let's start by considering the matrix response to an applied fascicle load. We must assume that the strain of the matrix is equal to the applied fibre strain so that

$$\varepsilon_m(t) = \varepsilon(t). \quad (3.1)$$

The matrix is modelled as linearly viscoelastic, meaning the stress and strain can be modelled in terms of creep response $J(t)$, and the relaxation function $G(t)$, which was introduced in Chapter 2. In terms of the relaxation response, consider the stress response from a small increment of strain $\delta\varepsilon$ at a time t_1 ,

$$\sigma(t) = G(t - t_1) \delta\varepsilon(t_1). \quad (3.2)$$

If a second strain is applied at t_2 , in addition to the first, the response of the strain is additive. Therefore, the overall stress can be represented as

$$\sigma(t) = G(t - t_1) \delta\varepsilon(t_1) + G(t - t_2) \delta\varepsilon(t_2). \quad (3.3)$$

For a series of N incremental strains the stress at time t_i , can be written as

$$\sigma(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N G(t - t_i) \delta\varepsilon(t_i). \quad (3.4)$$

This can be turned into an integral by taking the limit as the time increment decreases to 0,

$$\sigma(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t G(t-s)d\varepsilon(s), \quad (3.5)$$

which can be written as

$$\sigma(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t G(t-s)\frac{d\varepsilon(s)}{ds}ds. \quad (3.6)$$

The same method can be applied for the creep response leaving

$$\varepsilon(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t J(t-s)\frac{d\sigma(s)}{ds}ds. \quad (3.7)$$

If we integrate under the conditions $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, as $s \rightarrow -\infty$ and $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ as $s \rightarrow -\infty$ we are able to separate the immediate elastic response and the viscoelastic response to give

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon(t) &= \sigma(t)J(0) - \int_{-\infty}^t \sigma \frac{d}{ds}\{J(t-s)\}ds, \\ \sigma(t) &= \varepsilon(t)G(0) - \int_{-\infty}^t \varepsilon \frac{d}{ds}\{G(t-s)\}ds. \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Therefore if $G_m(t)$ is the matrix relaxation function, the matrix response can be modelled as

$$\sigma_m(t) = G_m(0)\varepsilon_m(t) + \int_0^t G'_m(t-s)\varepsilon_m(s)ds. \quad (3.9)$$

3.2 Single Fibril Response

Now I shall investigate the response of a single fibril to an applied fibre strain. Figure 4.1 below demonstrates how the parameters l_0 and L_0 represent the length of the fibril when the fibre is undeformed and the corresponding fibre length. We can assume $L_0 < l_0$.

Figure 3.1: A crimped fibril of length l_0 within a fibre with length L_0 . Image taken from [Shearer et al., 2020].

When the fibre is subjected to a force and stretched out, its length will change as a function of time. We can model the strain in the fibre as

$$\epsilon = \frac{\Delta L_0}{L_0}.$$

The fibre length at time t can be written as, $L(t) = L_0 + \Delta L(t)$ and the fibril length at time t is $l(t) = l_0 + \Delta l(t)$.

At time t the fibre and fibril strain can be defined as

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\Delta L(t)}{L_0} = \frac{L(t) - L_0}{L_0}, \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon_f(t) = \frac{\Delta l(t)}{l_0} = \frac{l(t) - l_0}{l_0}. \quad (3.10)$$

This is because strain measures how much an object is stretched so the strains of the fibre and fibril can be expressed as a function of their relative extension.

Let t_A be the time at which the fibril becomes taut, before this time there is no contribution to the overall stress from the fibrils. At $t = t_A$ the taut fibril will be the same length as the fibre so $L(t_A) = l_0$.

The strain in the fibril at $t = t_A$ is called the critical strain denoted ε_c , we can write the critical strain as an equation in terms of the undeformed fibre and fibril lengths,

$$\varepsilon_c = \varepsilon(t_A) = \frac{L(t_A) - L_0}{L_0} = \frac{l_0 - L_0}{L_0}. \quad (3.11)$$

It should be noted that this value is dependent on l_0 and as the fibrils are not all the same length the value of ε_c is unique to each individual fibril. The two lengths are equal after the critical strain is reached so $L + \Delta L = l + \Delta l$. If we define the fibril strain as

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{\Delta l_0}{l_0}$$

then the strain in the taut fibril can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_f^t(t) &= \frac{L(t) - l_0}{l_0} = \frac{L(t) - l_0 + L_0 - L_0}{l_0}, \\ &= \frac{(L(t) - L_0) - (l_0 - L_0)}{l_0}, \\ &= \frac{L_0}{l_0} \left(\frac{L(t) - L_0}{L_0} - \frac{l_0 - L_0}{L_0} \right), \\ &= \frac{L_0}{l_0} (\varepsilon(t) - \varepsilon_c), \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} (\varepsilon(t) - \varepsilon_c). \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

The superscript t demonstrates that the fibril is taut. Therefore the relationship between the applied fibre strain and fibril strain can be written as

$$\varepsilon_f = \begin{cases} 0 & \varepsilon < \varepsilon_c, \\ \frac{\varepsilon(t) - \varepsilon_c}{1 + \varepsilon_c} & \varepsilon \geq \varepsilon_c. \end{cases} \quad (3.13)$$

Therefore, following the same method used in the matrix response, the stress of the fibril is

$$\sigma_f(t) = \int_0^t G(t-s) \frac{d\varepsilon_f(s)}{ds} ds \quad (3.14)$$

which can be integrated to give the stress of the taut fibril as

$$\sigma_f^t(t) = G(0)\varepsilon_f^t(t) + \int_0^t G'(t-s)\varepsilon_f(s)ds, \quad (3.15)$$

note the integral covers the strain from $t = 0$ not just from when it becomes taut. This is important because the fibrils have different critical strains, when we consider these all together in the tendon we

must account for time when not all the fibrils are fully stretched out.

When the fibre is unloaded we can form an expression for the strain in terms of the creep function and time by inverting (3.15) until the fibril is slack. This gives,

$$\varepsilon_f(t) = J(0)\sigma_f(t) + \int_0^t J'(t-s)\sigma_f(s)ds. \quad (3.16)$$

This allows us to express the strain in a slack fibril as

$$\varepsilon_f^s(t) = \int_0^t J'(t-s)\sigma_f(s)ds, \quad (3.17)$$

the superscript s demonstrates the fibril's slackness.

This model implies that we should use different equations to work out the stress and the strain, depending on whether the fibril is taut or not. If taut, the fibril strain is determined from equation (3.13) and its stress should be determined by (3.15). When the fibril becomes slack at the point where the stress becomes zero ($\sigma_f = 0$), the strain is calculated according to equation (3.17). This equation is used until the fibril becomes taut once again post-reloading.

3.3 Fibre Response

To calculate the total stress in a fibre, we need to consider that each individual fibril which makes up the fibre, has a different critical strain rate due to varying crimp patterns. To do this, we can use the average stress in the fibrils and weight it by the probability of each strain occurring. By multiplying a probability density function for the critical strains $p(\varepsilon_c)$, with the stress response of the fibril and integrating we are left with the stress response of a fibre:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_F &= \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) \sigma_f(\varepsilon(t), \varepsilon_c) d\varepsilon_c \quad t \in [0, \infty), \\ \sigma_F &= \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) G(t-s) \frac{1}{1+\varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_c) d\varepsilon_c \quad t \in [0, \infty). \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

When choosing the probability density function, the only restriction faced is that it must give non-zero probabilities only for $\varepsilon_c \geq 0$. Emphasis is placed on the fact that the stress in the individual fibrils is dependent on the imposed strain and the critical fibril strain when the fibril is first taut, by use of the $\sigma_f(\varepsilon(t), \varepsilon_c)$ notation.

3.4 Tendon Response

To model the overall stress in the tendon, we must consider the stress in the fibre and the matrix together. This is done by taking the stress in the fibre and the matrix in proportion to their volume fractions. The fibril volume fraction is the volume of the fibrils which make up the fibre, divided by the overall volume. As the fibril volume fraction is ϕ , the matrix volume fraction will be $(1 - \phi)$, this means the total tendon stress can be calculated as $(1 - \phi)\sigma_m + \phi\sigma_F$ where σ_F is the fibre stress.

Therefore the total tendon stress can be calculated by

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(t) &= (1 - \phi)\sigma_m(t) + \phi \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) \sigma_F(\varepsilon(t), \varepsilon_c) d\varepsilon_c \quad t \in [0, \infty), \\ \sigma(t) &= (1 - \phi)\sigma_m(t) + \phi \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) G(t - s) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_c) d\varepsilon_c \quad t \in [0, \infty).\end{aligned}\tag{3.19}$$

Emphasis is placed on the fact that the stress in the individual fibrils is dependent on the imposed fibre strain and the critical fibril strain when the fibril is first taut, by use of the $\sigma_f(\varepsilon(t), \varepsilon_c)$ notation.

3.5 Incorporating Viscoelasticity into the Collagen Recruitment Model

In Chapter 2, I showed how the standard linear solid model was the most accurate rheological model in demonstrating the viscoelastic properties of tendons. Now the mathematics behind the collagen recruitment model has been laid out, it is possible to show how the results from the standard linear solid model can be incorporated into the collagen recruitment model. We can derive a general relaxation function from the standard linear solid model and substitute it directly into the collagen recruitment model. This will therefore tell us about the material properties of the tendon with the consideration of viscoelasticity.

To determine the general relaxation function, $G(t - s)$ of the standard linear solid model we need to write the constitutive equation in integral form. Recall the constitutive equation for the standard linear solid model is

$$\sigma + \frac{\eta}{E_1 + E_2} \dot{\sigma} = \frac{E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2} \varepsilon + \frac{E_1 \eta}{E_1 + E_2} \dot{\varepsilon},\tag{3.20}$$

once simplified and transformed by a Laplace transform we are left with

$$\begin{aligned}(E_1 + E_2) \bar{\sigma} + \eta s \bar{\sigma} &= E_1 E_2 \bar{\varepsilon} + E_1 \eta s \bar{\varepsilon}, \\ \bar{\sigma} &= \frac{E_1 E_2}{(E_1 + E_2) + \eta s} \bar{\varepsilon} + \frac{E_1}{(E_1 + E_2) + \eta s} \eta s \bar{\varepsilon}.\end{aligned}$$

Now factorise out η and multiply the first term by $\frac{s}{s}$ to give

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\sigma} &= \frac{E_1 E_2}{\left(\frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta} + s\right) s \eta} s \bar{\varepsilon} + \frac{E_1}{\frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta} + s} s \bar{\varepsilon}, \\ \bar{\sigma} &= \frac{E_1 E_2}{\eta} \cdot \frac{1}{s \left(\frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta} + s\right)} \cdot s \bar{\varepsilon} + E_1 \frac{1}{\frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta} + s} \cdot s \bar{\varepsilon}, \\ \bar{\sigma} &= \frac{E_1 E_2}{\eta} \cdot \frac{1}{s(\lambda + s)} \cdot s \bar{\varepsilon} + E_1 \frac{1}{\lambda + s} \cdot s \bar{\varepsilon},\end{aligned}$$

where $\lambda = \frac{E_1 + E_2}{\eta}$. After using the inverse Laplace transformation and the convolution theorem¹ we

¹See Appendix C

can return to the original variables,

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(t) &= \frac{E_1 E_2}{\eta} \int_0^t \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda(t-s)}}{\lambda} \cdot \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds + E_1 \int_0^t e^{-\lambda(t-s)} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds, \\ \sigma(t) &= \int_0^t \left[\frac{E_1 E_2}{\eta} \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda(t-s)}}{\lambda} + E_1 e^{-\lambda(t-s)} \right] \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds.\end{aligned}$$

By setting

$$A_0 = \frac{E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2}, \quad A_1 = E_1 - \frac{E_1 E_2}{E_1 + E_2}, \quad T_1 = \frac{\eta}{E_1 + E_2},$$

we can simplify this equation to give

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_f(t, \varepsilon_c) &= \int_0^t \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{d\varepsilon_f}{ds} ds, \\ \sigma_f(t, \varepsilon_c) &= \int_0^t \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon(s) - \varepsilon_c) ds.\end{aligned}\tag{3.21}$$

This equation allows us to work out the stress in a fibril upon loading under the assumption that the fibril can be described by the constitutive equation. By comparison with equation (3.15), it is easy to pick out the relaxation function $G(t-s)$ as $A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}}$. If we want to work out the total stress in the fibre upon loading we use

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_F(t) &= \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) \sigma_f(t, \varepsilon_c) d\varepsilon_c, \\ &= \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) \int_0^t \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon(s) - \varepsilon_c) ds d\varepsilon_c,\end{aligned}\tag{3.22}$$

whereas before $p(\varepsilon_0)$ is the probability density function which describes the critical strains where the fibrils become taut.

3.6 Viscoelastic Tendon Response

The total stress in the tendon can be modelled by consideration of the fibrils which make up the fibres and the extracollagenous matrix. As the extracollagenous matrix also has viscoelastic properties we can model it using the constitutive equation from the standard linear solid model, as we did with the fibrils. The stress of the matrix is therefore given by

$$\sigma_m(t, \varepsilon_c) = \int_0^t \left(A_0^M + A_1^M e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1^M}} \right) \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds,\tag{3.23}$$

A_0^M , A_1^M and T_1^M are material constants associated with the extracollagenous matrix. Therefore, the overall stress in the tendon will be the fibre stress plus the stress in the matrix, each weighted by their volume fractions:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(t) &= \phi \sigma_F(t) + (1 - \phi) \sigma_m(t) \\ &= \phi \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) \int_0^t \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon(s) - \varepsilon_c) ds d\varepsilon_c \\ &\quad + (1 - \phi) \int_0^t \left(A_0^M + A_1^M e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1^M}} \right) \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds.\end{aligned}\tag{3.25}$$

This constitutive equation effectively describes the different material behaviours tendons exhibit at arbitrary strain values. These include stress relaxation, hysteresis and non-linear stress-strain behaviour, which are all properties of viscoelastic materials. In the next chapter, I shall present various graphical representations of the model under different loading conditions. By comparing the graphs with typical stress-strain curves of tendons, we can decide whether our model is successful in predicting a tendon's response to an imposed stain. We can also physically observe if the properties of viscoelasticity are correctly described by the model, by examining the shapes of the graphs.

Chapter 4

Graphical Results for the Viscoelastic Collagen Recruitment Model

Using the derived model, we can now investigate how a tendon may behave under various loading conditions. To explore the viscoelastic behaviour of the tendon, I chose to consider three types of loading. These were: loading to a maximum imposed strain, loading under a gradually increasing strain and cyclic loading.

4.1 Investigating the Effects of the Fibril Volume Fraction

Before we test the model under the different loading conditions, we shall examine what the effect of altering the fibril volume fraction will have on our results. To determine the mechanical differences caused by varying the fibril volume fraction we shall plot stress-strain curves for values of $\phi = 1$, $\phi = 0.8$ and $\phi = 0.5$. These values were chosen, despite $\phi = 1$ being an unrealistic value, because no tendon is composed of entirely fibrils, it can be used to demonstrate when the matrix volume is so small, it is negligible. Additionally, $\phi = 0.5$ is used to demonstrate when there is an even proportion of matrix to fibrils. A tendon may have a smaller ratio of fibrils to matrix if there is damage to the fibrils in the form of a partial tear [Mengoni, 2019]. Microscopic damage is due to the breaking of fibrils which leads to a decreased fibril volume fraction. As we are investigating tendon failure, which is the result when all the fibrils tear, it may be useful to investigate the effect of altering the fibril volume fraction. Finally, a value of $\phi = 0.8$ is chosen as a more realistic value to represent the ratio of fibrils to matrix in a healthy tendon.

Figure 4.1 illustrates the different stress-strain curves for the values of $\phi = 1$, $\phi = 0.8$ and $\phi = 0.5$, under a strain increasing linearly at a rate of $1\%s^{-1}$. The values for the mean and standard deviation of the probability density function are 0.05 and 0.01, this implies that the critical strain of the fibrils is normally distributed around 5%. The fibril constitutive parameters are $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$ and the matrix constitutive parameters are $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2$. I chose these parameters as they produce results aligned with a tendon in real life. The value of A_0 added to A_1 should be a realistic value of the Young's modulus of a fibril, this is typically between 100MPa and $11,000\text{MPa}$ [Manssor et al., 2016]. Furthermore, A_0^M added to A_1^M should be a realistic value of the Young's modulus of the extracollagenous matrix. This exact value proved difficult to find as experimenting to find this value comes with many challenges. However, it is widely agreed that the Young's modulus of the extracollagenous matrix is significantly smaller than the Young's modulus of

a fibril. The Mathematica code for Figure 4.1 can be found in Appendix D.1.

Upon inspection of Figure 4.1, one can see that until a strain of 5% the three lines behave similarly, this suggests that the number of fibrils does not impact the mechanical response before strains of this value. As the critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%, this is expected as less than half the fibrils are still crimped before this strain. Therefore, these fibrils do not contribute to any resistance against deformation. After a strain of 5%, a higher proportion of fibrils become taut and differences within the responses can be seen.

Figure 4.1: The stress-strain curves for fibril volume fractions of 1, 0.8 and 0.5. The strain is increasing linearly with a rate of $1s^{-1}$. The values for the mean and standard deviation of the probability density function are 0.05 and 0.01, the fibril constitutive parameters are $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1s$ and the matrix constitutive parameters are $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2$.

Figure 4.1 shows that as the fibril volume fraction increases the gradient of the stress-strain curve increases. This implies that a higher fibril volume fraction corresponds to a stiffer material. An explanation for this is that tendons with higher fibril volume fractions have more individual fibrils which contribute to the tendon's overall resistance to deformation. Therefore, a greater force will be needed for the tendon to deform. Figure 4.1 agrees with this, as the curve for $\phi = 1$ has the highest overall maximum stress value for a fixed strain value, implying tendons with a higher proportion of fibrils can withstand higher strains.

Decreasing the fibril volume fraction to $\phi = 0.5$ results in the gradient of the stress-strain curve decreasing. Therefore, smaller fibril volume fractions lead to a less stiff material, which is less resistant to deformation. This is because fewer individual fibrils are contributing to the tendon's overall resistance to an applied strain. Therefore, more deformation is likely to occur. These results suggest that a tendon which has experienced microscopic damage on the fibril scale will be less stiff. As a result of this, the tendon is more likely to experience further damage as a decrease in fibrils results in a tendon that is more prone to deformation.

When investigating tendon failure, these results suggest that for strain-based failure, we would expect a tendon with a higher fibril volume fraction to have a high critical stress to failure value for a fixed critical strain to failure value. For stress-based failure, at a fixed critical stress to failure value, the strain to failure value would be less for a tendon with a greater fibril volume fraction. These types of failure are discussed in more detail in the next chapter.

4.2 Loading at Maximum Strain

The first loading condition we shall input into the collagen recruitment model is loading to the maximum strain value. This is the highest strain value a material can be subjected to before it snaps at the critical strain to failure value. The corresponding Mathematica code for the graphs presented in this section can be found in Appendix D.1. A graphical representation of this loading condition is displayed in Figure 4.2 where the maximum loading conditions investigated were 20% and 10%. It can be seen that immediately the imposed strain is the maximum strain value and this is maintained as time increases.

Figure 4.2: The loading condition with respect to time when we load to the maximum strain value. The maximum strain values investigated were 20% and 10%.

4.2.1 Single Fibril Response

The single fibril response to loading at maximum strain with respect to time is seen in Figure 4.3. In order to reach this result, the fibril constitutive parameters substituted into the model were $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$. Upon inspection of Figure 4.3, it can be seen that under a maximum loading condition the stress in the fibril immediately goes to a maximum stress value. Over time this decreases exponentially, implying stress is reduced under a constant deformation. This feature represents the stress relaxation property of viscoelastic materials. For an increased loading value, the rate at which the stress initially decreases, increases. This can be seen as the initial gradient of the curve, for a maximum strain of 20%, is steeper than the curve for 10%. This curve has the same initial shape as the standard linear solid model when subjected to a relaxation test. If we compare Figure 4.3 with Figure 2.12, we can see that the curves have the same shape up until the point of unloading in Figure 2.12. This is expected as we have used the standard linear solid model to model the fibrils.

4.2.2 Total Fibre Response

Figure 4.4 shows the stress-time graph for the response of a whole fibre loaded to two different imposed strains. The constitutive parameters remain the same and the critical strain values for the fibrils that make up the fibre are normally distributed around 5%. As in Figure 4.3, a stress relaxation property can be seen however, the maximum stress value is not reached immediately. This can be explained

Figure 4.3: The stress-time graph when a single fibril is loaded at the maximum strain values of 20% and 10%. The values for the fibril constitutive parameters are $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$.

by considering the impact of the multiple fibrils with varying critical strain values that make up the fibre. When subjected to an imposed strain, there will initially be a period where the fibre stretches out as the fibrils take different amounts of time to become un-crimped. Recall that the fibrils do not all have the same crimping pattern so have various critical strain values at which they become taut. Additionally, an accumulation of fibrils together means an increased resistance against deformation. This can be inferred by noting that the maximum stress in the individual fibril when loaded at 20% has a value of approximately 550MPa whilst in the fibre, it is approximately 380MPa which means there is less stress acting per unit area of the material.

Figure 4.4: The stress-time graph when a fibre is loaded at the maximum strain values of 20% and 10%. The values for the fibril constitutive parameters are $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$ and the critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%.

4.2.3 Tendon Response

To investigate the total tendon response we first need to consider the response of the extracollagenous matrix under an imposed strain. Figure 4.5 shows the stress response of the matrix with respect to time, the constitutive parameters are $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$. Since the matrix is also a viscoelastic material it does display a stress relaxation response but it is considerably less

dramatic than the stress relaxation response of the fibril. This allows us to conclude that for our chosen parameter values, it is the less viscoelastic component in comparison to the fibrils that make up the tendon.

Figure 4.5: The stress-time graph for the extracollagenous matrix when loaded at the maximum strain values of 20% and 10%. The values for the matrix constitutive parameters are $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$.

The total tendon response considers both the fibre response and the matrix response and can be seen in Figure 4.6. The parameters remain the same as in the previous examples and therefore it has a similar shape to Figure 4.4. The subtle difference is that the stress values are slightly less for a fixed value of time. For example, in Figure 4.4 the maximum stress value for an imposed strain of 20% on a fibre is approximately 380MPa whilst in Figure 4.6, the maximum stress reached for the entire tendon is approximately 340MPa. This can be explained as the tendon consists of both fibres and the extracollagenous matrix, which has been shown by Figure 4.5 to only relax by approximately 1MPa and therefore is considerably less responsive to deformation under a constant load. This aligns with the conclusions made previously by altering the fibril volume fraction, as we found that a lower proportion of fibrils in the tendon lead to an increased likelihood of deformation. Also note how for a smaller strain value of 10% the relaxation curve is more similar to that of the matrix in Figure 4.5, this is because at smaller strains there are more slack fibrils which are stress-free so the relaxation behaviour is more similar to the matrix. At larger strains, more fibrils become taut, so the relaxation behaviour is more similar to the individual fibrils. This phenomenon is due to the tendon having a strain-dependent non-linear stress-relaxation property. The effect of this can be more easily seen in Figure 4.7, which is the tendon stress-relaxation non-dimensionalised on the peak stress, for maximum strain values of 10% and 5%. A smaller maximum strain of 5% is chosen so the difference in the curves is more obvious.

4.3 Loading at a Linearly Increasing Strain

Now we shall investigate the results produced from the model when we have a strain value which is increasing linearly. This is useful when we are interested in tendon failure as many experiments increase the loading strain, to find the critical strain to failure value when the tendon ruptures. Once we introduce failure criteria into the model, we will be able to compare the graphs produced from the model with real-life data collected from experiments and conclude if our model is accurate in describing the material properties of tendons. The corresponding Mathematica code for the graphs

Figure 4.6: The stress-time graph for the tendon when loaded at the maximum strain values of 20% and 10%. The values for the fibril constitutive parameters are $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$ and the critical strain of the fibrils is normally distributed around 5%. The values for the matrix constitutive parameters are $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$.

Figure 4.7: The tendon stress-relaxation non-dimensionalised on the peak stress for strain values of 10% and 5%. The parameter values are the same as in Figure 4.6.

presented in this section can be found in Appendix D.2. When investigating the material response under a linearly increasing strain, the same values of $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$, $T_1 = 1\text{s}$, $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$ were used as the constitutive parameters. The critical strain of the fibrils is also normally distributed around 5%. Figure 4.8 shows the imposed strain with respect to time for rates increasing linearly by $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$. Figure 4.9 shows the strain a single fibril experiences under the imposed strain. The critical strain of the fibril is 1% which is why the curves do not cross through the origin. For a strain increasing at $1\%s^{-1}$ we would expect a fibril to become taut after 1s and at 0.5s for a strain increasing at a rate of $2\%s^{-1}$. This is shown on the graph at the point where the lines cross the x-axis.

4.3.1 Single Fibril Response

Figure 4.10 shows the stress-time graph for a singular fibril with a critical strain of 1%, for strains increasing linearly at rates of $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$. For a rate of $1\%s^{-1}$, the curve passes through the x -axis at 1s, this is the time it takes the fibril to become taut and experience stress. For $2\%s^{-1}$ it takes 0.5s, which is expected as the rate of strain is increasing at a rate double of $1\%s^{-1}$, so the time taken will be halved.

Figure 4.8: The imposed strain with respect to time. The strain is linearly increasing with a rate of $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$.

Figure 4.9: The strain experienced by an individual fibril with a critical strain of 1% at strain rates increasing linearly at $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$. The fibril experiences no stress until it becomes taut at times of 0.5s and 1s.

Figure 4.11 shows the stress-strain graph for a singular fibril with a critical strain of 1%, at strains increasing linearly for rates of $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$. Both lines pass through the x -axis at a strain of 1%, as expected as this is the critical strain value for the fibril. Initially, both Figures 4.10 and 4.11 display the phenomenon of strain softening - as the strain increases the gradients of the curves decrease. Strain softening is a property of viscoelastic materials where the rate at which stress increases, decreases with a continuous increase of strain. In Figure 4.11 we can see that at a higher strain rate the effects of strain softening are less, meaning that when the curves take a linear shape, the value of stress is larger at a fixed strain. This implies a higher deformation resistance at increased rates of strain. The reason for this is a viscous resistance due to greater frictional resistance [Candau et al., 2020].

4.3.2 Total Fibre Response

Figures 4.12 and 4.13 show the response of a total fibre under a linearly increasing strain. As the fibre is made up of many fibrils with various critical strains, which have been modelled as normally distributed around 5%, the effect from strain softening decreases in Figure 4.12. In Figure 4.13, as the strain initially increases, the gradients of the curves increase. This is also due to the consideration of many different fibrils with various critical strains. This curve looks more similar to the typical stress-strain curve of a tendon in Figure 1.5, where a toe region and linear region can be seen. For the higher rate of strain, the stress value is larger at fixed strains like it also was for the fibril. This is due

Figure 4.10: The stress-time response of a single fibril with a critical strain of 1% for rates increasing at $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$

Figure 4.11: The stress-strain curve for a fibril with critical strain of 1% under a linearly increasing strain rates of $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$.

to the same reasons explained previously, where there is an increase in viscoelasticity from frictional resistance.

Figure 4.12: The stress-time response for a fibre with the constitutive parameters $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%. The rates are increasing at $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$.

4.3.3 Tendon Response

Finally, a tendon response to a linearly increasing imposed strain is shown in Figures 4.14 and 4.15. The curves are a similar shape to the fibre response, however, note how the stress values are slightly

Figure 4.13: The stress-strain response for a fibre with the constitutive parameters $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%. The rates are increasing at $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$.

less as fixed strain values. This is due to the consideration of the viscoelastic extracollagenous matrix which also makes up the tendon. At an increased strain rate the value of the stress is still greater at fixed strains due to the reasons explained previously. If we compare Figure 4.15 with the typical stress-strain curve of a tendon in Figure 1.5 we can see the similarities. The toe region is between strains of roughly 0% – 7% and for strains above 7%, the linear region begins. This is aligned with what we expected, based on a typical tendon stress-strain curve.

Figure 4.14: The stress-time response for a tendon with the constitutive parameters $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$, $T_1 = 1\text{s}$, $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%. The rates are increasing at $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$.

4.4 Cyclic Loading

Finally, we shall impose a strain from cyclic loading, this will allow us to conclude if the model successfully predicts hysteresis in a tendon. Recall hysteresis is when upon loading and unloading a viscoelastic material, the loading and unloading curve on a stress-strain graph will not follow the same path due to energy being lost as heat due to internal friction. This means that under each consecutive loading the maximum stress value reached will decrease. The corresponding Mathematica code for the graphs presented in this section can be found in Appendix D.3. Figure 4.16 shows the imposed strain under cyclic loading. The constitutive parameters in the model and the distribution remain the same as in the previous examples.

Figure 4.15: The stress-strain response for a tendon with the constitutive parameters $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$, $T_1 = 1\text{s}$, $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%. The rates are increasing at $1\%s^{-1}$ and $2\%s^{-1}$.

Figure 4.16: The imposed strain the tendon is subjected to, under cyclic loading conditions for a maximum strain of 20% and 10%.

Figure 4.17 shows the tendon response to cyclic loading with respect to time. You can see that after one cycle the peak is less than the cycle previously, as expected. This is because energy is lost as heat during loading and therefore the maximum stress will be reduced. Figure 4.18 shows the stress-strain graph of the tendon under cyclic loading. It is clear to see that the loading and unloading curves do not follow the same paths for both values of imposed strain. Therefore, we can conclude that our model when describing the mechanical behaviour of tendons at arbitrary strain rates, exhibits the phenomenon of hysteresis.

Overall, the graphs produced from the derived collagen recruitment model indicate that this model can successfully predict the mechanical behaviour of tendons at arbitrary strain rates. The graphs have collectively displayed the expected viscoelastic phenomena of, stress relaxation and in particular strain dependant stress-relaxation which is non-linear, non-linear stress-strain behaviour and hysteresis. We can now have confidence that our model will produce results that are aligned with the behaviour of real tendons when investigating their mechanical behaviour and can begin to incorporate failure into the model. In the next chapter, I shall introduce various failure criteria for a tendon and investigate the circumstances under which tendons are likely to fail. This will lead us nicely into incorporating failure criteria into our model.

Figure 4.17: The stress response of the tendon under cyclic loading conditions. The values for the fibril constitutive parameters are $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$ and the critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%. The values for the matrix constitutive parameters are $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$.

Figure 4.18: The stress-strain graph for the tendon under cyclic loading conditions. The values for the fibril constitutive parameters are $A_0 = 1000\text{MPa}$, $A_1 = 2000\text{MPa}$ and $T_1 = 1\text{s}$ and the critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%. The values for the matrix constitutive parameters are $A_0^M = 90\text{MPa}$, $A_1^M = 10\text{MPa}$ and $T_1^M = 2\text{s}$.

Chapter 5

Introducing Failure into the Viscoelastic Collagen Recruitment Model

Now we have an equation which accounts for the viscoelasticity of a tendon when predicting mechanical responses, we can begin to investigate the conditions under which tendon failure occurs. There are two kinds of tendon failure criteria, stress-based criteria and strain-based criteria. Both shall be explored in this chapter. This project is the first time failure criteria has been incorporated into a collagen recruitment model, whilst also assuming the viscoelasticity of a tendon. Whilst failure and viscoelasticity have previously been modelled separately, I am the first person to consider these in a single model. As viscoelasticity is a material property of the tendon, our model will be more accurate in predicting the circumstances under which tendons fail than a model which does not assume viscoelasticity.

5.1 Failure Criteria

As previously noted in the explanation of the stress-strain curve in Figure 1.5 for a tendon, it is only once all the fibrils are taut that the tendon stiffness stops increasing in the linear region and permanent damage on the fibril scale begins [Gregory et al., 2021]. This is supported by evidence found by Zitany et al. [Zitany et al., 2017], who detected damage in the fibrils at molecular level in a rat tail tendon, only once the tendon had been stretched past the linear region. The tendon fails when it reaches the macroscopic failure region, in this region, it can be assumed that most of the fibrils have been damaged leading to tendon failure. A continued increase in strain levels will lead to irreversible changes in the collagen fibres and permanent stretching will occur. Tendon failure is due to the breakage of collagen-collagen or collagen-elastin bonds. This happens at a critical stress to failure value or ultimate tensile strength, for human tendons this value ranges from 45-125 MPa. For the critical stress to failure value, there is a corresponding critical strain to failure value, which in human tendons is between 9% – 35% [Hench and Jones, 2005].

The overall function of any tendon is enabling movement by providing an attachment from muscle to bone, to transfer a force generated by muscle contraction to the skeleton [Thorpe et al., 2014]. Despite this, there exist more specific specialisations of tendons which allow us to broadly categorise

them into two different groups. Positional tendons act to position the limb for movement whilst energy-storing tendons must reduce the energy lost from locomotion by acting as elastic springs during movement. Unlike positional tendons, energy-storing tendons must withstand high forces and exhibit compliance, allowing the tendon to elongate for maximum energy storage [Thorpe et al., 2014]. The forces applied to energy-storing tendons are often done so in a highly repetitive manner, an example of this is when running. An extreme example, but one that demonstrates this point is that during a marathon the Achilles tendon endures a repetitive loading force about 25,000 times. Furthermore, the tension experienced at each loading during ground contact, exceeds twelve times the body weight [Quigley et al., 2018].

Experimental results collected at the University of Utah, have shown a difference in tendon failure between positional and energy-storing tendons. Fascicles collected from the rat tail tendon (RTT), and the rat flexor digitorum longus (FDL) tendon represented the positional and energy-storing tendons. The samples were stretched at incremental levels of strain and observations about the nature of their failure were made. In general, the RTT collagen fibrils exhibited plastic deformation more readily than the FDL fibrils which demonstrated a more abrupt failure [Lin et al., 2020]. This is demonstrated on the stress-strain curves for each tendon in Figure 5.1. These differences can be explained by the arrangement of the intermolecular collagen cross-links. When subjected to a strain the alpha chains which make up the collagen molecule, begin to slide disrupting the triple helical structure of the tendon and eventually causing damage. Energy-storing tendons have a higher valency and density of cross-links compared to positional tendons, which allows them to have a greater resistance to inter-molecular sliding [Eekhoff et al., 2018].

Figure 5.1: The stress-strain curves for the RTT and the FDL. It can be seen that the RTT shows a plastic deformation as the strain increases whereas the FDL failure is more abrupt. Image taken from [Lin et al., 2020].

In this project, I shall be investigating tendon failure exhibited by energy-storing tendons. The three most common energy-storing tendons that humans rupture include, the Achilles tendon, the quadriceps and the rotator cuff. The quadriceps are a group of four muscles above the kneecap which form the patellar tendon and the rotator cuff is located in the shoulder and facilitates the rotation of the arm and the bicep, this in turn acts as a flexor of the elbow. When a tendon of this type ruptures under high amounts of strain, it is reported that a snap or a pop can be heard or felt which demonstrates the abrupt failure an energy-storing tendon can experience.

Figure 5.2 below shows the stress-strain graph for the human patellar tendon, the critical stress to failure value can be read when the tendon fails and the stress decreases to 0%. The strain percentage at the maximum point of stress is the critical strain to failure value. Figure 5.3 shows the stress-strain

curves plotted from experimental data from tests taken on different turkey tendons. The data is only recorded to the critical stress value which is the maximum point on the graph.

Figure 5.2: The stress-strain curves for the collagen fibrils taken from human patellar tendons. It can be seen that failure occurs when the line instantly decreases to 0 as the fibrils snap. The mean critical stress \pm a standard deviation was recorded at 540 ± 140 MPa and the mean critical strain \pm a standard deviation was $20 \pm 1\%$. Image taken from [Svensson et al., 2013]

Figure 5.3: The stress-strain curves for different tendons in a turkey hindlimb (A). The specific muscles were the flexor hallucis longus (FHL), flexor perforans et perforatus digiti 3 (FPPD3), tibialis cranialis (TC), flexor perforans digiti 3 (FPD3), extensor digitorum longus (EDL), and the gastrocnemius complex (GA). Graph (B) shows the corresponding elastic modulus against the strain. Due to challenges not all GA and TC specimens were tested to failure. The corresponding data for Figure 5.2 is in the table below. Image and data taken from [Matson et al., 2012].

Tendon	critical stress (MPa)	critical strain (%)
EDL	68.22 ± 13.83	9.30 ± 1.91
FPD3	66.83 ± 14.34	9.16 ± 1.64
FPPD3	112.37 ± 9.39	10.67 ± 1.20
FHL	107.25 ± 14.12	9.14 ± 1.01

5.2 Incorporating Failure into the Mathematical Model

We are now in a position to add failure criteria to our collagen recruitment model. As previously mentioned, this is the first time that both viscoelasticity and failure have been incorporated into a collagen recruitment model. It is not known what mechanism causes tendon failure, therefore I shall investigate both strain-based failure and stress-based failure. I shall lay out two different failure criteria for each circumstance. Additionally, it is possible to introduce failure criteria on the fibrils at the microscopic level but also by considering a failure criterion on the entire tendon on the macroscopic level. I shall investigate the difference between failure criteria on both levels. For all failure criteria, we shall assume constantly increasing applied strain. By examining the graphs produced by the different models and comparing them with the graphs produced from the experimental data presented earlier in this chapter, we will be able to determine which failure criteria most accurately replicates real-life tendon behaviour when it fails.

5.2.1 Strain-Based Failure

Microscopic Level

For strain-based failure on the microscopic scale, we can impose a failure criterion on the fibril. We will assume that if the imposed strain exceeds the critical strain to failure value then the fibril will snap and the strain will go to zero. Therefore the new relationship between the applied fibre strain and the fibril strain can be written as

$$\varepsilon_f^* = \begin{cases} 0 & \varepsilon < \varepsilon_c, \\ \frac{\varepsilon(t) - \varepsilon_c}{1 + \varepsilon_c} & \varepsilon \geq \varepsilon_c, \\ 0 & \frac{\varepsilon(t) - \varepsilon_c}{1 + \varepsilon_c} > \varepsilon_{cf}, \end{cases} \quad (5.1)$$

where ε_{cf} is the critical strain to failure value of the fibril. We can now substitute this new value ε_f^* , for the fibril strain into our collagen recruitment model. Therefore the new stress response of the fibres is

$$\sigma_{F1}^*(t) = \int_0^t p(\varepsilon_c) \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon^*}{ds} H(\varepsilon^*(s) - \varepsilon_c) ds d\varepsilon_c. \quad (5.2)$$

We must also assume the matrix has a critical strain to failure value and impose an additional matrix failure criterion. We will assume that if the imposed strain exceeds the matrix strain to failure value, the matrix will fail and the stress response will go to zero. This can be represented as

$$\sigma_{m1}^* = \begin{cases} \sigma_m & \varepsilon < \varepsilon_{mf}, \\ 0 & \varepsilon \geq \varepsilon_{mf}, \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

where ε_{mf} , is the matrix critical strain to failure value and $\sigma_m = \int_0^t \left(A_0^M + A_1^M e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1^M}} \right) \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds$. Therefore, the overall tendon response with the addition of strain-based failure criteria on the fibrils and the matrix can be represented as

$$\sigma_1^* = \phi \sigma_{F1}^*(t) + (1 - \phi) \sigma_{m1}^*(t). \quad (5.4)$$

This equation imposes failure criteria on the microscopic scale, next we shall derive an equation which assumes strain-based failure on the macroscopic level.

Macroscopic Level

When imposing strain-based failure on the macroscopic level, we assume that if the imposed strain exceeds the value of the critical strain to failure value of the tendon, the entire tendon will snap and the stress will go to zero. This can be represented as

$$\sigma_{T1}^*(t) = \begin{cases} \phi\sigma_F(t) + (1 - \phi)\sigma_m(t) & \varepsilon < \varepsilon_{ct} \\ 0 & \varepsilon \geq \varepsilon_{ct}, \end{cases} \quad (5.5)$$

where ε_{tf} is the critical strain to failure value for the entire tendon and

$$\begin{aligned} \phi\sigma_F(t) + (1 - \phi)\sigma_m(t) = & \\ \phi \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) \int_0^t \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon(s) - \varepsilon_c) ds d\varepsilon_c & \\ + (1 - \phi) \int_0^t \left(A_0^M + A_1^M e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1^M}} \right) \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds. & \end{aligned} \quad (5.6)$$

5.2.2 Stress-Based Failure

Microscopic Level

For stress-based failure, the critical stress to failure value for the fibril is denoted σ_{cf} . If the stress in the fibril exceeds this value then we can assume the fibril will snap and the stress will go to zero. The stress in the taut fibril can therefore be represented as

$$\sigma_f^*(t) = \begin{cases} \sigma_f & \sigma_f < \sigma_{cf}, \\ 0 & \sigma_f \geq \sigma_{cf}. \end{cases} \quad (5.7)$$

where σ_{cf} , is the fibril critical stress to failure value and $\sigma_f = \int_0^t \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon(s) - \varepsilon_c) ds d\varepsilon_c$. We can then model the stress in the fibre as

$$\sigma_{F2}^* = p(\varepsilon_c) \sigma_f^*. \quad (5.8)$$

Additionally, we need a stress-based failure criterion on the matrix to model the tendon response. We can assume that if the stress in the matrix exceeds the critical stress to failure value for the matrix, the matrix will fail and the stress will go to zero. This can be represented as

$$\sigma_{m2}^*(t) = \begin{cases} \sigma_m & \sigma_m < \sigma_{cm}, \\ 0 & \sigma_m \geq \sigma_{cm}, \end{cases} \quad (5.9)$$

where σ_{cm} is the critical stress to failure value of the matrix and $\sigma_m = \int_0^t \left(A_0^M + A_1^M e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1^M}} \right) \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds$. Therefore, the overall tendon response with stress-based failure criteria imposed on the fibrils and the matrix can be written as

$$\sigma_2^* = \phi\sigma_{F2}^* + (1 - \phi)\sigma_{m2}^*. \quad (5.10)$$

Macroscopic level

We will now impose a stress-based failure criterion on the macroscopic level. We can assume that if the stress in the entire tendon exceeds a critical stress to failure value for the tendon then the tendon will snap and the stress will go to zero. This can be modelled as

$$\sigma_{T2}^*(t) = \begin{cases} \phi\sigma_F(t) + (1 - \phi)\sigma_m(t) & \sigma(t) < \sigma_{ct}, \\ 0 & \sigma(t) \geq \sigma_{ct}, \end{cases} \quad (5.11)$$

where σ_{ct} is the critical stress to failure value for the tendon and

$$\begin{aligned} & \phi\sigma_F(t) + (1 - \phi)\sigma_m(t) = \\ & \phi \int_0^\infty p(\varepsilon_c) \int_0^t \left(A_0 + A_1 e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1}} \right) \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_c} \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} H(\varepsilon(s) - \varepsilon_c) ds d\varepsilon_c \\ & + (1 - \phi) \int_0^t \left(A_0^M + A_1^M e^{-\frac{t-s}{T_1^M}} \right) \frac{d\varepsilon}{ds} ds. \end{aligned} \quad (5.12)$$

We now have models for both strain and stress-based failure criteria, imposed on both the microscopic and macroscopic levels. I shall now present graphical representations of the models and compare them with the graphs produced from experimental data. This will allow us to conclude whether imposing failure criteria on the microscopic level or macroscopic level will produce results which most accurately reflect real-life tendon behaviour.

5.3 Graphical Results

5.3.1 Microscopic Level

Figures 5.4 and 5.5 show the graphical results of our failure model with the failure criteria imposed on the microscopic level. Figure 5.4 displays the graph for strain-based failure criteria for strains increasing linearly at rates of $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$. The critical strain of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5% and the fibril volume fraction is $\phi = 0.8$, the critical strain to failure value for the fibrils is 10% and the critical strain to failure value for the matrix is 15%. I chose these values as we assume that the matrix can withhold higher strain values as it only fails once all the fibrils fail. Figure 5.5 imposes stress-based criteria. The values of the parameters are the same as in Figure 5.4 with the exception that we impose a critical stress to failure value for the fibrils of 150MPa and for the matrix of 16MPa.

By examining both figures, we can see that the rate of strain affects the corresponding strain or stress failure value. For strain-based criteria, at a higher rate of strain, the stress failure value is greater than at a lower strain rate. Furthermore, for stress-based failure criteria, a higher rate of strain corresponds to a smaller critical strain to failure value. This is due to reasons discussed previously, where at increased strain rates there is a higher deformation resistance due to viscous resistance from a greater frictional resistance.

5.3.2 Macroscopic Level

Figures 5.6 and 5.7 show a graphical representation of the model with a failure criterion imposed on the macroscopic level for rates of strains of $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$. The parameters inputted are consistent with those inputted on the microscopic scale however for the strain-based failure the tendon critical strain to failure value was 15%. For the stress-based failure criterion, the tendon critical stress to failure value was 100MPa.

As with the graphs produced at the microscopic level, at the macroscopic level, we can also see the effects of strain rate dependence. For strain-based failure, the corresponding stress to failure value is

Figure 5.4: The stress-strain curve for strain rates of $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$ with an imposed strain-based failure criteria on a microscopic level. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%, the fibril volume fraction is $\phi = 0.8$, the critical strain to failure value for the fibrils is 10% and the critical strain to failure value for the matrix is 15%.

Figure 5.5: The stress-strain curve for strain rates of $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$ with an imposed stress-based failure criteria on a microscopic level. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%, the fibril volume fraction is $\phi = 0.8$, the critical stress to failure value for the fibrils is 150MPa and the critical stress to failure value for the matrix is 16MPa.

greater at a higher strain rate. For stress-based failure, the corresponding strain to failure value is less for the higher strain rate.

5.4 Discussion

In general, we can conclude that when failure criteria is imposed on a microscopic scale the nature of the tendon failure is much more gradual than when it is imposed on the macroscopic scale. In Figures 5.6 and 5.7 the failure is much more abrupt than in Figures 5.4 and 5.5. Additionally, we can conclude that both strain-based and stress-based failure criteria produce results that agree with each other, in terms of the shapes of the graphs. This means that more work needs to be done to determine the level of quantitative agreement with experimental data for different tendons for both types of failure criteria, as both will accurately describe the material behaviour with time-independent.

Figure 5.6: The stress-strain curve for strain rates of $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$ with an imposed strain-based failure criterion on the macroscopic level. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%, the fibril volume fraction is $\phi = 0.8$ and the critical strain to failure value for the tendon is 15%.

Figure 5.7: The stress-strain curve for strain rates of $1s^{-1}$ and $2s^{-1}$ with an imposed stress-based failure criterion on the macroscopic level. The critical strains of the fibrils are normally distributed around 5%, the fibril volume fraction is $\phi = 0.8$, and the critical stress to failure value for the tendon is 100MPa.

When we compare the graphs produced earlier on in the chapter which display experimental results, with the graphs produced from our models, we can see that when failure criteria is imposed on the microscopic scale, the shape is similar to the energy-storing tendon stress-strain graph in Figure 5.1. The graphs produced on the macro-scale are more similar to Figure 5.2 which shows experiments on individual fibrils. This is aligned with what we might expect as Figure 5.2 only investigates individual fibril failure, the fibrils collectively make up the tendon and will fail at different imposed strains due to their crimp pattern. Therefore, for a whole tendon, we would expect the failure to be less abrupt as fibrils snap over time. Figure 5.1 displays this more gradual failure. The different curves for fibrils taken from the same tendon in Figure 5.2 can perhaps be explained by the phenomenon of rate dependence that our models predict. If the experiments on the individual fibrils were done at varying rates of strain we would expect different recorded critical stress to failure and strain to failure values.

The stress-strain graph in Figure 5.3 stops recording data once the tendon has begun to fail,

therefore we can not observe the nature of the failure. However, if this data was collected we would expect the graph to display a gradual failure like that in Figure 5.1. Additionally, observe that the shape of the curves in Figure 5.3 are similar in shape to the curves produced by all the models up to the point of failure. This implies that the model we have derived is successful in predicting the material behaviour of tendons up to the point of failure. The fact that the stress-strain graph for an energy-storing tendon in Figure 5.1 has a shape which is aligned with our model with failure criteria on the microscopic scale, allows us to conclude that imposing failure criteria on the microscopic scale will lead to an increase in accuracy if we are to use our model to predict tendon behaviour in real life. This would lead me to favour failure criteria imposed on the microscopic level over the macroscopic level.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

6.1 Summary of Key Findings

In conclusion, we have found that developing a model on the microscopic scale leads to results which accurately reflect the macroscopic properties of a tendon. In particular, when investigating the circumstances under which tendons fail, imposing failure criteria on the microscopic level produces results which are more accurate in mirroring the results from real-life experimental data. Furthermore, we have found that the constitutive equation derived from the standard linear solid model is sufficient in demonstrating the viscoelasticity of a tendon. Our model can display the expected viscoelastic phenomena of stress relaxation and in particular strain dependant stress-relaxation which is non-linear, non-linear stress-strain behaviour and hysteresis. As this is the first instance where failure criteria have been incorporated into a collagen recruitment model which accounts for the viscoelasticity of a tendon, the conclusions made about the effects of imposing the failure criteria on the microscopic level are significant to research on the mechanics of tendon failure. Our model can explain the nature of tendon failure on the microscopic level which improves understanding of injuries. The effect of fibril crimping leads to varying critical strain values which in turn means that the individual fibrils will have various critical strain to failure values. Therefore, they will not all fail at the same time but will have a distributed strain to failure value which explains the gradual shape of the stress-strain failure graph. Additionally, we found that when imposing failure criteria we can produce accurate results for both stress-based and strain-based criteria which are both time-dependent.

6.2 Further Work

If we wanted to extend the research for this dissertation, we could attempt to determine the true values of the parameters for specific tendons using non-linear regression to fit experimental data. Once these values have been established, we could use our model to make predictions about specific tendons. A database of critical stress and strain to failure values could be estimated from the model by inputting the corresponding parameters for specific tendons. This would be useful in preventing injury as we would know the conditions under which tendons fail, and precautions could be taken to prevent this. Additionally, it would be interesting to further investigate the differences between the nature of failure between positional and energy-storing tendons. For example, does one type of tendon favour a stress-based failure over a strain-based failure and what are the qualitative differences (if there are any) between these types of failure? Finally, we could further investigate if failure is solely based on either

stress or strain-based criteria, or if in reality, it is a composite of the two. On the other hand, failure may not be based on either of these but a strain energy value. This is the energy stored in a body due to deformation and the significance of this value with respect to failure, could be investigated.

Appendix A: Step Functions

A.1 Heaviside Function

The Heaviside function is defined as

$$\mathcal{H}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x < 0, \\ 1 & x \geq 0, \end{cases}$$

it is a discontinuous function where the value is zero for negative arguments and one for positive arguments.

The integral of the Heaviside function is defined as

$$\int_{-\infty}^x \mathcal{H}(t) dt = \begin{cases} 0 & x < 0, \\ x & 0 < x, \end{cases}$$

which can be written in terms of the Heaviside function as

$$\int \mathcal{H}(x) dx = x\mathcal{H}(x),$$

A.2 Dirac Function

The derivative of the Heaviside function is the Dirac delta function which is denoted by the δ -function. The δ function is a discontinuous generalised function which takes the value of zero everywhere apart from at the origin. It can be represented as

$$\delta(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \neq 0 \\ \infty & x = 0. \end{cases}$$

A more formal definition of the δ function is

$$\delta_a(x) = \frac{1}{a\sqrt{\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{a^2}\right) \quad \text{as } a \rightarrow 0.$$

Appendix B: Laplace Transforms

The Laplace transform is an integral transform defined as

$$\mathcal{L}\{f(t)\} \rightarrow \bar{f}(s) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} f(t) dt.$$

It is a linear transform which takes the x value into a new complex variable s and is useful as it can convert differential equations into purely algebraic equations. The inverse Laplace transform is defined as $\mathcal{L}^{-1}\{\bar{f}(s)\} \rightarrow f(t)$. Below are some useful Laplace transforms whose results are used in this dissertation.

B.1

$$\mathcal{L}\{1\} \rightarrow \frac{1}{s}$$

B.2

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{\mathcal{H}(t)\} &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} \mathcal{H}(t) dt \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} dt \\ &= \frac{1}{s} \end{aligned}$$

B.3

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{\delta(t)\} &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} \delta(t) dt \\ &= e^{-st} \Big|_{t=0} \\ &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

B.4

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}\{\mathcal{H}(t-T)\} &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} \mathcal{H}(t-T) dt \quad \text{where } T \in R \\ &= \int_0^T e^{-st} dt \cdot 0 + \int_T^{\infty} e^{-st} dt \cdot 1 \\ &= \left[-\frac{1}{s} e^{-st} \right]_T^{\infty} \\ &= \frac{1}{s} e^{-sT} \end{aligned}$$

B.5

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}\{\delta(t-T)\} &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} \delta(t-T) dt \quad \text{where } T \in R \\
&= e^{-st} \Big|_{t=T} \\
&= e^{-sT}
\end{aligned}$$

B.6

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}\{e^{-\alpha t}\} &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} e^{-\alpha t} dt \\
&= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-(s+\alpha)t} dt \\
&= \left[-\frac{1}{s+\alpha} e^{-(s+\alpha)t} \right]_0^{\infty} \\
&= \frac{1}{s+\alpha}
\end{aligned}$$

B.7

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}\left\{\frac{1-e^{-\alpha t}}{\alpha}\right\} &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} (1-e^{-\alpha t}) dt \\
&= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} dt - \int_0^{\infty} e^{-(s+\alpha)t} dt \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{s+\alpha} \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{s(s+\alpha)}
\end{aligned}$$

B.8

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}\{e^{-\alpha(t-T)} \mathcal{H}(t-T)\} &= \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\alpha(t-T)} e^{-st} \mathcal{H}(t-T) dt \\
&= \int_0^T e^{-\alpha t - st + \alpha T} dt \cdot 0 + \int_T^{\infty} e^{-\alpha t - st + \alpha T} dt \cdot 1 \\
&= \left[-\frac{1}{\alpha+s} e^{-(\alpha+s)t + \alpha T} \right]_T^{\infty} \\
&= \frac{e^{-sT}}{\alpha+s}
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix C: The Convolution Theorem

The convolution theorem is an important result of Fourier theory that maintains that the convolution of two functions in real space is equal to the product of their respective Fourier transforms. I.e

$$\mathcal{F}\{f * g\} = \mathcal{F}\{f\} \cdot \mathcal{F}\{g\}$$

where $*$ is the convolution operator defined as

$$(f * g)(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\alpha)g(t - \alpha)d\alpha = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t - \alpha)g(\alpha)d\alpha.$$

The Convolution theorem holds for Laplace transforms also as long as the convolution operator is restricted to $t > 0$.

Appendix D: Mathematica Code for The Collagen Recruitment Model

D.1 Linearly Increasing Strain

```

e[t_,r_] := t*r (*Strain function*)

\[Epsilon][t_,ec_,r_] := If[e[t,r]/100<ec,0,((e[t,r]/100-ec)/(1+ec))] (*Fibril strain*)

A0=1000; (*Fibril constitutive parameters*)
A1=2000;
T1=1;
\[Sigma]f[t_,ec_,r_] := Quiet[NIntegrate[(A0+A1 Exp[-(t-\[Tau])/T1])HeavisideTheta
[e[\[Tau],r]-ec]D[\[Epsilon][\[Tau],ec,r],\[Tau]]/(1+ec),{\[Tau],0,t}]] (*Fibril stress*)

f[\[Epsilon]c_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_] := PDF[TruncatedDistribution[{0,\[Infinity]},
NormalDistribution[\[Mu],\[Sigma]]],\[Epsilon]c] (*Probability density function*)

\[Sigma]F[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_] := NIntegrate[Hold[f[ec1,\[Mu],\[Sigma]]] (*Fibre stress*)

\[Sigma]f[t,ec1,r]],{ec1,0,Infinity},AccuracyGoal->8]

A0M=90; (*Matrix constitutive parameters*)
A1M=10;
T1M=2;
\[Sigma]M[t_,r_] := Quiet[NIntegrate[(A0M+A1M Exp[-(t-\[Tau])/T1M])D[e[\[Tau],r]/100,
\[Tau]],{\[Tau],0,t}]] (*Matrix stress*)

\[Sigma][t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_,\[Phi]_] := \[Phi] \[Sigma]F[t,\[Mu],\[Sigma],r]+(1-\[Phi])\[Sigma]M[t,r]
(*Tendon stress*)

Plot[{e[t,1],e[t,2]},{t,0,5}, PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Strain %"},AxesStyle->Thick,
LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*
Imposed strain graph*)

Plot[{100\[Epsilon][t,0.01,1],100\[Epsilon][t,0.01,2]},{t,0,10},PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)",
Strain %"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s",
"Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*Fibril strain graph*)

Plot[{\[Sigma]f[t,0.01,1],\[Sigma]f[t,0.01,2]},{t,0,20},PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Stress (
MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s",
Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*Fibril stress-time graph*)

StressListrate1=Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma]f[t,0.01,1]},{t,0,20,0.1}]];

```

```

StressListrate2=Quiet[Table[{e[t,2],\[Sigma]f[t,0.01,2]},{t,0,10,0.1}]];

ListPlot[{StressListrate1,StressListrate2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold,Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*Fibril stress-strain graph*)

fibreStressListrate1=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma]F[t,0.05,0.01,1]},{t,0,20,0.6}]];
fibreStressListrate2=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma]F[t,0.05,0.01,2]},{t,0,20,0.6}]];

ListPlot[{fibreStressListrate1,fibreStressListrate2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold,Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*Fibre stress-time graph*)

fibreStressstrainListrate1=Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma]F[t,0.05,0.01,1]},{t,0,20,0.5}]];
fibreStressstrainListrate2=Quiet[Table[{e[t,2],\[Sigma]F[t,0.05,0.01,2]},{t,0,10,0.5}]];

ListPlot[{fibreStressstrainListrate1,fibreStressstrainListrate2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold,Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*Fibre stress-strain graph*)

Tendonrate1=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,1,0.8]},{t,0,20,0.5}]];
Tendonrate2=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,2,0.8]},{t,0,20,0.5}]];

ListPlot[{Tendonrate1,Tendonrate2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold,Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*Tendon stress-time graph*)

TStressListrate1=Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,1,0.8]},{t,0,20,0.5}]];
TStressListrate2=Quiet[Table[{e[t,2],\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,2,0.8]},{t,0,10,0.5}]];

ListPlot[{TStressListrate1,TStressListrate2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold,Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate = 2%/s"}] (*Tendon stress-strain graph*)

TtStressListrate1=Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,1,0.5]},{t,0,20,0.5}]];
TtStressListrate=Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,1,1]},{t,0,20,0.5}]];

ListPlot[{TtStressListrate,TStressListrate1,TtStressListrate1},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold,Medium],PlotLegends->{"\[Phi]=1","\[Phi]=0.8","\[Phi]=0.5"}] (*change in fibril volume fraction graph*)

```

D.2 Loaded to Max Strain

```

\[Epsilon][t_,\[Epsilon]max_]:=If[t<0,0,If[t<0.01,100\[Epsilon]max t,\[Epsilon]max]] (*Imposed strain*)

A0=1000; (*Fibril constitutive parameters*)
A1=2000;
T1=1;
\[Sigma]f[t_,ec_,\[Epsilon]max_]:=Quiet[NIntegrate[(A0+A1 Exp[-(t-\[Tau])/T1])HeavisideTheta[\[Epsilon][\[Tau],\[Epsilon]max]-ec]D[\[Epsilon][\[Tau],\[Epsilon]max],\[Tau]]/(1+ec),{\[Tau],0,t}]] (*Fibril stress*)

Plot[{\[Sigma]f[t,0.01,0.2],\[Sigma]f[t,0.01,0.1]},{t,0,5},PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold,Medium],PlotLegends->{"Loading strain = 20%","Loading strain = 10%"}] (*Fibril stress-time graph*)

```

```

\[Sigma]F[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,\[Epsilon]max_]:=NIntegrate[Hold[f[ec1,\[Mu],\[Sigma]]\[Sigma]f[t,ec1,\[Epsilon]max]],{ec1,0,Infinity},AccuracyGoal->8]

StressList20Percent=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma]F[t,0.05,0.01,0.2]},{t,0.5,0.2}]];
StressList10Percent=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma]F[t,0.05,0.01,0.1]},{t,0.5,0.2}]];

ListPlot[{StressList20Percent,StressList10Percent},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)",
Stress (MPa)},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Loading strain =
20%" , "Loading strain = 10%"}] (*Fibre stress-time graph*)

A0M=90; (*Matrix constitutive parameters*)
A1M=10;
T1M=2;
\[Sigma]M[t_,\[Epsilon]max_]:=Quiet[NIntegrate[(A0M+A1M Exp[-(t-\[Tau])/T1M])D\[Epsilon][\[Tau],\[Epsilon]max],\[Tau]],{\[Tau],0,t}] (*Matrix stress*)

\[Sigma][t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,\[Epsilon]max_,\[Phi]_]:=\[Phi] \[Sigma]F[t,\[Mu],\[Sigma],\[Epsilon]max]
+(1-\[Phi])\[Sigma]M[t,\[Epsilon]max]

Tendon20=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,0.2,0.8]},{t,0.5,0.2}]];
Tendon10=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,0.1,0.8]},{t,0.5,0.2}]];

ListPlot[{Tendon20,Tendon10},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Stress (MPa)"},
AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Loading strain = 20%" , "
Loading strain = 10%"}] (*Tendon stress-time graph*)

Tendonscale10=Quiet[\[Sigma][0.01,0.05,0.01,0.1,0.8]];
TendonND10=Table[{Tendon10[[i]][[1]],Tendon10[[i]][[2]]/Tendonscale10},{i,1,Length[Tendon10]}];

Tendon5=Quiet[Table[{t,\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,0.05,0.8]},{t,0.5,0.2}]];

Tendonscale5=Quiet[\[Sigma][0.01,0.05,0.01,0.05,0.8]];
TendonND5=Table[{Tendon5[[i]][[1]],Tendon5[[i]][[2]]/Tendonscale5},{i,1,Length[Tendon5]}];

ListPlot[{TendonND5,TendonND10},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Nondimensionalised
Stress"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Loading strain = 5%" ,
"Loading strain = 10%"}] (*Non-Dimensionalised graph*)

```

D.3 Cyclic Loading

```

\[Epsilon][t_,\[Epsilon]max_]:=If[t<0,0,If[t<1,\[Epsilon]max t,If[t<2,\[Epsilon]max(2-t),If[t<3,\[Epsilon]
max(t-2),If[t<4,\[Epsilon]max(4-t),0]]]]] (*Imposed strain*)

Plot[{100\[Epsilon][t,0.2],100\[Epsilon][t,0.1]},{t,0,4},PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Strain (%)"
},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Max loading strain to 20%" , "
Max loading strain to 10%"}] (*Imposed strain graph*)

Hys1=Quiet[Table[{100\[Epsilon][t,0.1],\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,0.1,0.8]},{t,0.5,0.1}]];
Hys2=Quiet[Table[{100\[Epsilon][t,0.2],\[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,0.2,0.8]},{t,0.5,0.1}]];

ListPlot[{Hys1,Hys2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,
LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Loading strain = 20%" , "Loading strain = 10%"}]
(*Tendon stress-strain*)

```

```
tendonhys1=Quiet[Table[{t, \[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,0.1,0.8]},{t,0,5,0.1}]];
tendonhys2=Quiet[Table[{t, \[Sigma][t,0.05,0.01,0.2,0.8]},{t,0,5,0.1}]];

ListPlot[{tendonhys1,tendonhys2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Time (s)","Stress (MPa)"},
  AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Loading strain = 20%" , "Loading
  strain = 10%"}] (*Tendon stress-time graph*)
```

D.4 Strain-Based Failure

D.4.1 Micro-Scale

```
\[Epsilon][t_,ec_,r_]:= If[e[t,r]/100<ec,0,((e[t,r]/100-ec)/(1+ec))

A0=1000; (*Fibril constitutive parameters*)
A1=2000;
T1=1;
\[Sigma]f1[t_,ec_,r_,\[Epsilon]F_]:= If[\[Epsilon][t,ec,r]<\[Epsilon]F,Quiet[NIntegrate[(A0+A1 Exp[-(t-\[
  Tau])/T1])HeavisideTheta[e\[Tau],r-ec]D[\[Epsilon][\[Tau],ec,r],[Tau]]/(1+ec),{[Tau],0,t}],0] (*
  Fibril stress under micro strain-based criterion*)

\[Sigma]F1[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_,\[Epsilon]F_]:=NIntegrate[Hold[f[ec1,\[Mu],\[Sigma]]\[Sigma]f1[t,ec1,r,\[
  Epsilon]F]],{ec1,0,Infinity},AccuracyGoal->8] (*Fibre stress under micro strain-based criterion*)

\[Sigma]Mc[t_,r_,em_] := If[e[t,r]/100<em,Quiet[NIntegrate[(A0M+A1M Exp[-(t-\[Tau])/T1M])D[e\[Tau],r
  ]/100,\[Tau]],{[Tau],0,t}],0] (*Matrix stress under micro strain-based criterion*)

\[Sigma]t1[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_,\[Epsilon]F_,\[Phi]_,em_] := \[Phi] \[Sigma]F1[t,\[Mu],\[Sigma],r,\[
  Epsilon]F]+(1-\[Phi])\[Sigma]Mc[t,r,em]

tendonfail1 = Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma]t1[t,0.05,0.01,1,0.1,0.8,0.15]},{t,0,17,0.2}]];
tendonfail2 = Quiet[Table[{e[t,2],\[Sigma]t1[t,0.05,0.01,2,0.1,0.8,0.15]},{t,0,8.5,0.1}]];

ListPlot[{tendonfail1,tendonfail2},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %","Stress (MPa)"},
  AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate =
  2%/s"}] (*Tendon stress-strain graph with strain-based failure imposed on the micro-scale*)
```

D.4.2 Macro-Scale

```
\[Sigma]t[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_,\[Phi]_,ef_]:=If [e[t,r]/100<ef,\[Phi] \[Sigma]F[t,\[Mu],\[Sigma],r]+(1-\[
  Phi])\[Sigma]M[t,r],0] (*Tendon stress under macro strain-based criterion*)

tendontest = Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma]t[t,0.05,0.01,1,0.8,0.15]},{t,0,15,0.5}]];
tendontest1 =Quiet[Table[{e[t,2],\[Sigma]t[t,0.05,0.01,2,0.8,0.15]},{t,0,7.5,0.5}]];

ListPlot[{tendontest,tendontest1},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %","Stress (MPa)"},
  AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate =
  2%/s"}] (*Tendon stress-strain graph with strain-based failure imposed on the macro-scale*)
```

D.5 Stress-Based Failure

D.5.1 Micro-Scale

```

\[Sigma]f2[t_,ec_,r_,\[Sigma]F_]:= If\[Sigma]f[t,ec,r]<\[Sigma]F,\[Sigma]f[t,ec,r],0) (*Fibril stress
under micro stress-based criterion*)

\[Sigma]F2[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_,\[Sigma]F_]:=NIntegrate[Hold[f[ec1,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]]\[Sigma]f2[t,ec1,r,\[
Sigma]F]],{ec1,0,Infinity},AccuracyGoal->8] (*Fibre stress under micro stress-based criterion*)

\[Sigma]Mc[t_,r_,m\[Sigma]F_ ]:= If\[Sigma]M[t,r]<m\[Sigma]F,Quiet[NIntegrate[(A0M+A1M Exp[-(t-\[Tau])/T1M
])D[e[\[Tau],r]/100,\[Tau]],{\[Tau],0,t}],0] (*Matrix stress under micro stress-based criterion*)

\[Sigma]2[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_,\[Phi]_,\[Sigma]F_,m\[Sigma]F_]:= \[Phi] \[Sigma]F2[t,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r,\[
Sigma]F_]+(1-\[Phi])\[Sigma]Mc[t,r,m\[Sigma]F_

test4 = Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma]2[t,0.05,0.01,1,0.8,150,16]},{t,0,20,0.2}]]
test5 = Quiet[Table[{e[t,2],\[Sigma]2[t,0.05,0.01,2,0.8,150,16]},{t,0,10,0.1}]]

ListPlot[{test4,test5},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %","Stress (MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,
LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain rate = 2%/s"} ] (*
Tendon stress-strain graph with stress-based failure imposed on the micro-scale*)

```

D.5.2 Macro-Scale

```

\[Sigma]fail[t_,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r_,\[Phi]_,\[Sigma]cf_ ]:=If[ \[Phi] \[Sigma]F[t,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r]+(1-\[
Phi])\[Sigma]M[t,r] < \[Sigma]cf,\[Phi] \[Sigma]F[t,\[Mu]_,\[Sigma]_,r]+(1-\[Phi])\[Sigma]M[t,r],0] (*
Tendon stress under macro stress-based criterion*)

tendonstressfail=Quiet[Table[{e[t,1],\[Sigma]fail[t,0.05,0.01,1,0.8,100]},{t,0,20,0.5}]];
tendonstressfail1=Quiet[Table[{e[t,2],\[Sigma]fail[t,0.05,0.01,2,0.8,100]},{t,0,10,0.5}]];

ListPlot[{tendonstressfail,tendonstressfail1},Joined->True,PlotRange->All,AxesLabel->{"Strain %", "Stress (
MPa)"},AxesStyle->Thick,LabelStyle->Directive[Bold, Medium],PlotLegends->{"Strain rate = 1%/s","Strain
rate = 2%/s"} ] (*Tendon stress-strain graph with stress-based failure imposed on the macro-scale*)

```

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